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**IT-FACILITATED
CROP ROTATION PLANNING SYSTEM**

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This Special Project titled

**Implementation of an IT-Facilitated
Crop Rotation Planning System**

is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the Master of Information Systems.

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Biographical Sketch

Born on September 20, 1989, in Quezon City, I am Honey Mae A. Samson, a devoted and results-driven Business Systems Analyst with over a decade of hands-on expertise in analyzing, designing, and implementing business processes and technology solutions.

I hold a Bachelor's Degree in Computer Engineering from the Polytechnic University of the Philippines. Building on this foundation, I pursued my Master of Information Systems at the University of the Philippines – Open University.

With a profound dedication to my field, I have served as an Information Systems consultant for esteemed organizations such as the United Nations Development Programme and the World Health Organization. My professional journey has allowed me to contribute to the innovative digital solutions of non-profit organizations and private institutions.

My field of expertise and research revolves around Innovative Digital Solutions for non-profit organizations. Having engaged with reputable international entities, my work has focused on bringing technological advancements to the forefront of organizations dedicated to global development.

Beyond the academic realm, I find joy in building and collecting hobby toys, immersing myself in the details of craftsmanship. Additionally, I indulge in the strategic challenges of chess, finding a balance between recreation and the stimulating exercise of logical thinking.

In conclusion, my academic journey reflects a steadfast commitment to excellence, a passion for Management Information Systems and digital solutions, and an unyielding pursuit of knowledge. I eagerly anticipate contributing meaningfully to the academic community and making a positive impact beyond.

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Lastly to my partner in life and partner in this study (the Operations Manager of the Villegas Organiks), **Mr. Joshua Samuel B. Villegas**, for cooperation and for giving time and effort in terms of providing me all the needed information to establish the proposed solution and providing support throughout this venture.

Dedicated to:

All Existing and Aspiring Filipino Farmers

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Abstract

It is a common assumption that profit and sustainability are opposed when it comes to organic farming because organic agriculture is highly dependent on natural fertilization strategies.

The Villegas Organiks located at Malvar, Batangas is a farm whose advocacy is in promoting organic farming. The farm serves as a techno-demo farm that teaches interested farmers the ways of organic farming. However, as a techno-demo farm, the Villegas Organiks farm puts less importance on their personal crop production since they mainly focus on the information dissemination of the organic farming technologies. They consider their crop production as merely an add-on since these crops are used as training grounds for the farmers in their program.

For the sake of maximizing profitability and sustainability, the introduction of farm management tools is essential in giving a more modern approach to agriculture. The goal is to provide a system that incorporates both production and business resulting in better monitoring of inventory, production schedule, and sales.

The pilot implementation of a technology-based Crop Rotation Planning System considered the availability of the resources and facilities in servicing agriculture institutions and prioritized the need to see all crop productions and plans in a single place and share these plans to encourage all farmers to enhance agro-ecosystem health through organic farming.

The student being the technology enabler, in collaboration with Villegas Organiks being the pilot implementer, designed and customized a web-based platform for crop rotation planning. Based on the needs and priorities, implementation schedule, technology capabilities, and limitations, and available resources, the main service that is currently being offered in the pilot implementation is focused on the reduction of data entry load and allow Villegas Organiks operators and farmers to better manage their production cycle and reduce time and resource wastage.

Chapter I

Introduction

Proper crop rotation planning is an integral part of organic farming. It is imperative that the farm management have the right information on crop rotation and companion planting to bridge the gap between faulty rotation and weighing fixed and fluctuating production circumstances: market, farm size, labor supply, climate, soil type, growing practices, etc. Moreover, crop rotation must consider what conditions one crop will leave the soil for the succeeding crop. The consequences of faulty rotation may result in relying on chemical fertilizers to complete the required nutrients needed which in turn converts into additional expense to the farmers. Further negligence may result in severely damaged soil with heavy dependency on external nutrient sources (a dextrose approach) to continue production. Recovering from this would take several years.

To get a holistic view of the crop rotation planning challenges and a more detailed understanding of a particular function of the concerned farmers and farm operators, the student chose to study the need, uses, and benefits of an IT-facilitated crop rotation planning system.

The student conducted information systems analysis and design study which covers the review and analysis of data sources, processing rules for crop production, and generation of outputs and reports regarding crop related information. One of the study's focuses is to analyze the business needs of a farm supporting organic farming.

In 2011 to 2012, the Cooperative and Sustainable Agriculture and Entrepreneurship Learning Center, with the technical and financial assistance from the Department of Agriculture, has embarked in a community-based organic seed production project, mainly vegetables, food crops and staple crops as well as in integrated upland rice production followed by field crops such as soybeans, sorghum, cassava and corn, including two urban organic gardening projects in Quezon City and Marikina City, Metro Manila.¹

One of its cooperative members is the Villegas Organiks Farm which is a developed agriculturally landscaped organic farm complex that mixes nature's beauty through ornamental and vegetable gardening during sustainable growth of agro-forest and fruit trees, crops, livestock, and fish.

The study to modernize the farm management process is currently assisting the Villegas Organiks and the Cooperative and Sustainable Agriculture and

¹ Data available online; see the References section.

Entrepreneurship Learning Center in trial testing the functionalities of the technology-based Crop Rotation Planning System (CRPS). The key implementers led by the student selected Villegas Organiks as the pilot implementor. The rationale of the study of the modern agriculture within the pilot phase is to provide an easy access to the best organic agriculture practices and technological advances, one of which is Crop Rotation Planning procedure. The study would also develop knowledge of what information is needed on a regular basis for decision making purposes and how it is sought and used by the Villegas Organiks with the help of an internal information system.

This manuscript will focus on the pilot implementation of the Villegas Organiks implementation of a technology-based Crop Rotation Planning System (CRPS) covering activities and outputs from the preparation of the pilot phase to the evaluation of the different farm functionalities accessed through the system. The report also includes the initial draft of the planned phase two implementation and roll out.

All outputs of the study will be translated into a Toolkit of Farm Innovation and Crop Rotation Planning process guide which all the stakeholders will use when carrying out their roles and responsibilities in implementing the IT-facilitated CRPS.

Chapter II

Review of Existing Alternatives

The purpose of this chapter is to outline and present the processes and procedures followed by the student in identifying, analyzing, and planning how to select the right solution, and benefit from it in relation to Villegas Organiks needs.

Solution Objectives

Requirement Name	Requirement Description	Rationale / Objectives
Crop Record Management	Villegas Organiks should be able to see all crop records are in one place and easily accessible.	(1) To be able to organize crop information, rotation, and scheduling in an easily accessible, centralized database. (2) To provide a structural architecture that would improve profitability, lessen waste / spoilage, increase operational efficiency, and improve productivity.
	Crop records should be organized for compliance reporting	
	System should be able to identify crop and log movement histories.	
Field Management	Villegas Organiks should be able to identify all field records and its histories.	
Crop Rotation Planning	System should be able to improve and centralize Villegas Organiks' crop and rotation planning.	
Farm Set Up	Villegas Organiks should be able to set up and configure their farm information, and other farm related records and documents.	
User and Role Accountability	Villegas Organiks should be able to manage and administer all system users.	
	Users should be accountable for any changes on the crop record, field record, farm information, and crop rotation plan.	

Table 1: Solution Objectives

The student conducted a comparative market analysis based on the industry's technology standards and best practices. The following procedures were followed:

- (1) Created and maintained a plan for the acquisition of solution components.

- (2) Considered future flexibility for capacity additions, transition costs, risk, and upgrades throughout the project lifecycle.
- (3) Reviewed all acquisition plans.
- (4) Considered the risk, costs, benefits, and technical conformance with enterprise architecture standards.
- (5) Assessed and documented the degree to which solutions are required to adapt business processes to leverage the solution benefits.
- (6) Followed required reviews at key decision points during the procurement process.

Solutions Comparison Matrix

Criteria	Odoo	Farmos	Ground-Up
System features			
Villegas Organiks should be able to see all crop records are in one place and easily accessible.	✓	✓	✓
Crop records should be organized for compliance reporting	✓	✓	✓
System should be able to identify crop and log movement histories.	✓	✓	✓
Villegas Organiks should be able to identify all field records and its histories.	✓	✓	✓
System should be able to improve Villegas Organiks' crop and rotation planning.	✓	✓	✓
Villegas Organiks should be able to set up and configure their farm information, and other farm related records and documents.	✓	✓	✓
Villegas Organiks should be able to manage and administer all system users.	✓	✓	✓
Users should be accountable for any changes on the crop record, field record, farm information, and crop rotation plan.	✓	✓	✓
Server hosting	Included	Included	To be purchased separately
Total Implementation Cost in PHP	FREE	3,750.00	500,000.00
Total Transition Cost in PHP	Self-Service	Self-Service	Included
Development/configuration duration	4 weeks	4 weeks	8 weeks
Flexibility	✓	x	With Cost
Upgrades	✓	x	With Cost

Table 2: Software Solutions Comparison Matrix

What Makes Odoo Stand Out?

System Functionality

Odoo ERP is a comprehensive out-of-the-box system that is made up of an integrated suite of business models. As outlined in the comparison matrix, all solutions offer essential software characteristics (specific and general functionalities), but Odoo has a range of specialized options for different processes, including agriculture model. It also anticipated technological advancements which will extend their software's lifespan and make customization and upgrade less frequent.

Cost

Currently, there are two Odoo versions available in the market – one is *Community* edition and the other one is *Enterprise* edition. The enterprise version is licensed-based which includes 'paid' features while the community version is an open-sourced tool or 'free' to use, it can be downloaded and hosted on own client's server.

Both editions offer flexibility to selected industry type such as Agriculture and eLearning. Specifically in the Product Lifecycle Management model (which will be the backbone of the Villegas Organiks Crop Rotation Planning System), Odoo offers the following modules for free:

- (1) Inventory
- (2) Manufacturing
- (3) Website Builder
- (4) System Settings which include Organization Information, User Management, Permissions Management, Languages Set Up, etc.

Implementation and Timeline

- (1) Over the past 5 years, more than 95% of Odoo implementations have been successful, which stands in stark contrast to other solution providers.²
- (2) Working on site is inefficient to get things done. All necessary build activities can be done remotely because their application is hosted in the cloud and can easily be accessed over the internet.
- (3) Development and implementation do not require developers. Odoo has a linear out-of-the-box models and features which do not require custom development. The configuration, data import, and specific functionality alignment can be done in parallel by a non-developer resource.
- (4) The solution is shaped progressively throughout the phase; thus, the project team will only work in short cycles to deliver the required functionalities.

² Based on Odoo Implementation Methodology document.

Chapter III

Project Details

A. Overview

The project is the design, implementation, and establishment of an IT-facilitated Crop Rotation Planning System (or CRPS). This application serves as the electronic hub where farmers and farm owners can easily access the information on crop production protocols, organic farming best practices, and service offerings of the Villegas Organiks. The information system is linked to the Villegas Organiks farm website which serves as the crops and products information portal.

For this project, the aim was to determine the surrounding problematic and success key issues regarding the current crop rotation planning processes and the implementation of a technology-based fertilization techniques. The project is focused on crop rotation planning.

B. Theoretical Framework

Before the development, the student determined what requirements are important for the farm operators, they should have a clear idea of the system's purpose and how it will benefit their organization. The technique used by the student for this project is Business Process Improvement (BPI).³ It helped the student lead the Villegas Organiks through the steps so that the vision of the system can be developed.

Step 1: Identifying Business Processes

As part of the BPI analysis strategy, the student first identified all key business processes, including its sub-processes, and other activities, then analyzed and considered the movement of information and resources between the farm divisions. The information was gathered from process users, owners, and experts.

The image contains two screenshots of Excel spreadsheets. The left screenshot shows a spreadsheet titled 'Iceberg Lettuce Production Protocols' with columns for Date, Days, Activities, Inputs/Quantity/Equipment, and Details. It lists activities like 'Procurement of Materials' and 'Land Preparation'. The right screenshot shows a spreadsheet titled 'Bell Pepper Production Protocols' with columns for Date, Days, Activities, Inputs/Quantity/Equipment, and Details. It lists activities like 'Watering / Irrigation', 'Harvesting', and 'Spraying Wood Vinegar'.

Figures 1 & 2: Sample Crop Production Protocols in Excel format

³ BPI is one of the process improvement methodologies to analyze, identify, and improve a process within a business to enhance overall quality.

Step 2: Document the Process

The tasks and decisions that define the flow of information through a workflow are included in the process documentation. All the resources required and all the influences which affect the operations of a crop production, directly or indirectly, are documented. The concerned divisions and job functions involved in the crop process were also enumerated. The As-Is activities were also identified and documented. This includes documenting the details of inputs, outputs, interfaces, and relationship to the existing process flows and understanding the organizational structure and stakeholders involved.

Position	Role
Farm Operations Manager	Manage farm operations such as crop production protocols, and expenses. Manage farm orders.
Farmers	Perform farmland preparation, sowing, transplanting, watering, harvesting works.
Farm Consultant	Propose crop rotation plans.
Farm Owner	Oversee the farm operations, orders, and expenses.

Table 3: High-Level Process Map Position

Table 3 shows the respective position and roles of each member in the high-level process map of the Villegas Organiks with regards to crop rotation planning system.

Step 3: Analyze and Measure the Process

The student conducted several interviews with people involved directly or indirectly with the As-Is process, but the information was mainly gathered from farm's operations manager. During the interviews, the student gathered information about process structure, as well as process performance data and evaluated each process to validate the current priority level and consider opportunities for improvement. The existing process flow was subsequently reviewed and integrated into the new flows, wherever possible. Possible process improvements, discussed during the interviews, were also integrated into the new process flows. Hence, a detailed examination of the As-Is system was performed by the student.

Step 4: Improve the Process

The draft documentation was then reviewed by the important stakeholders to make sure that the student 's analysis was proceeding as required by them. The potential benefits from improving the current crop rotation planning system were considered, and any likely problems with the system were also conceived during the analysis of the As-Is activities. The student identified the various opportunities and options available for improvement. The student then designed user driven, non-technical conceptual process and data models using

context diagrams, dataflow diagrams and entity relationship diagrams of the To-Be System. The BPI analysis technique concluded with the project team developing a prototype of the proposed system. The student developed new prototypes of process flows, system mock screens, high level data flow diagram, and defined new reporting requirements to re-optimize the business processes.

Figure 3: Conceptual Structure of the CRPS

The web-application system has been established using Odoo ERP Community Edition.

Feasibility Analysis

The student determined the feasibility of the CRPS project, which were evaluated based on three criteria: Technical Feasibility, Economic Feasibility, and Organizational Feasibility.

(1) Technical Feasibility

The student first examined the organization's capability to complete this project based on technological capability, information systems familiarity, compatibility, and project size.

Based on the comprehensive observation, the Villegas Organiks has multiple resources whose skills can be utilized to assist in the implementation of the system. They are conducting performance management and report generation using MS Excel and other computer applications for different farm projects. However, these resources are not familiar with the technology that the system will employ. There is therefore a need to utilize an Information Systems Analyst to help with the development and implementation of the CRPS.

The student, being a full time IS Subject Matter Expert (SME) volunteered to assist in the actual development work of the proposed solution.

(2) Economic Feasibility

This section outlines the intangible benefits of having an Information System to the Villegas Organiks.

- By having access to information from various sources from a single platform, farmers and operators will no longer need to rely on limited data or their instinct.
- Since critical data is available to all users, it allows them to make informed decisions on key aspects of crop production. In addition, farm owners can query the data themselves with little to no IT support, saving more time and money.
- By transforming data into purposeful information, decision makers can perform more functional, precise, and reliable analysis and create more useful reports with ease.

Since the CRPS is not directly connected to increased revenue or substantial cost savings, the tangible costs outweigh the intangible benefits. The intangible benefits described above make the CRPS a worthwhile investment. It is important to note that the purpose of this project is not to cut costs for the Villegas Organiks farm, but rather to provide the existing farmers and aspiring farmers with the information they need in the way that is most convenient for them to view it.

(3) Organization Feasibility

The perceptions of staff of Villegas Organiks about information technology were at a high level. The availability of the management information system in their farm will help them improve crop rotation planning procedures, increase efficiency among farmers, improve output, and save time.

The idea was also presented to the members of the Cooperative. During the meeting, Dr. Isagani Catedral mentioned that the IS would be indispensable in the ways of organic farming as it can support the farm operations and strategic planning in the agricultural sector. The farm owner, Mr. Pablito Villegas, also expressed his appreciation on the initiative and hoped for more features that would enhance the capacities of fertilization strategies.

Since the people in decision making, analysis and process are involved, the student believed that the implementation of an internal Information System will be bound to be smooth because the feeling of imposition and ambush is expunged. This should mean little organizational technology resistance.

The Villegas Organiks and Cooperative can both play a significant role in advocating the system's adoption. Over and above, the Villegas Organiks Farm

Operators, if well trained on their crucial role, can influence the viewpoint of other farms and farmers towards organic farming.

C. Technologies Used

The system is based on standard technologies and based on tried and tested components.

- Odoo is a Client/Server system that works over an IP network. Both server and client extensions are packaged as *modules* which are optionally loaded in a *database*.
- Odoo module is a collection of functions and data that target a single purpose.
- Odoo server-side programming language is Python.
- Odoo uses Object-Oriented technologies.
- The presentation tier is a combination of HTML5, JavaScript and CSS.
- Odoo records its data with a PostgreSQL relational database.
- Odoo business objects are modeled with an Object Relational Mapping (ORM) system.
- Odoo allows PNG, JPEG, GIF, and SVG file formats.
- Odoo uses ReportLab for report generation in PDF.
- Odoo uses XML for several purpose: describing data, view, reports, data transport (XML-RPC).
- Odoo's traffic analysis tool is Google Analytics.

D. System Design

a. General Functionalities

General functionalities have been imposed:

- (1) The system catered to browser responsive, worked on desktop browser and mobile browser.
- (2) The system design is a tabbed application, and its main menu is being used to navigate features of the system and guide the user to the action or information they seek.
- (3) The system has a registration and logging in process.
- (4) Error messages were stored centrally and categorized. These messages displayed in a form of a pop-up messages. For fill-in forms, error messages are being displayed for unacceptable values. The system also provides a semantic and syntactic information in error messages, e.g., characters not accepted in the Date field (syntactic), March dates range from 1 to 31 (semantic).

- (5) Field validations are also being handled both the client side and server side as applicable to process. Default focus is set to the first control on the screen.
- (6) Search functions with filtering options are available on each module.
- (7) The system provides users with the ability to send and receive system alerts on certain pre-configured data update events.
- (8) Other general functionalities are as follows:
 - User and Access Management
 - Data and Records Management
 - Content Management System (for the Website contents)
 - Generation of Reports and Dashboards
 - Audit Trail Procedures

b. System Architecture

The backbone of the Crop Rotation Planning System is *Odoo ERP*. It is a multitenant, three-tier architecture system: application tier for processing, presentation tier for user interface and database tier for data storage. The applying tier itself is written as a core, multiple further modules may be put in to make a selected configuration of Odoo architecture.⁴

Figure 4: Odoo Architecture

Odoo as several ORMs uses the conception of 'model'. A model is an Associate in Nursing authoritative specification of however some knowledge is structured, affected, and manipulated. As noted, a model is written as a Python category. The category encapsulates something there's to understand concerning the model: the various fields composing the model, default values to be used once making new records, constraints, and so on. It conjointly holds the dynamic side of the info it controls. Strategies on the category may be written to implement any business wants (for instance, what to try to upon user action, or upon progress transitions).⁵

⁴ Data available in Odoo Website; see the References section.

⁵ Data available in Odoo Website; see the References section.

There are 2 completely different models. One is solely referred to as ‘model’, and the second is termed ‘transient model’. The 2 models give an equivalent capability with one difference: transient models are mechanically cleared from the information (they may be cleansed once some limit on the number of records is reached, or once they are untouched for a few times).

Figure 5: Odoo Module Structure

c. System Features

The following activities can be performed in Crop Rotation Planner System:

- (1) Recoding of and easy access to all crop and field records.
- (2) Centralizing and organizing records for compliance reporting.
- (3) Easy tracking of fields and crops movements and histories.
- (4) Improving crop production and rotation planning.
- (5) Easy configuration of farm information, employee information, and client records.
- (6) Centralized monitoring of crop requests and orders.
- (7) Generation of reports and dashboards.

Figure 6: CRPS Functional Decomposition Diagram

d. Database Design

Database Structure
Decimal Accuracy
Assets
Models
Fields
Fields Selection
Model Constraints
ManyToMany Relations
Attachments
Logging
Profiling

Table 4: High-Level Database Structure

Usage	Digits
Product Price	2
Discount	2
Stock Weight	2
Volume	2
Product Unit of Measure	2
Payment Terms	6

Table 5: Decimal Precision (decimal.precision)

Model	Model Description	Type	Transient Model
account.account	Account	Base Object	FALSE
account.analytic.account	Analytic Account	Base Object	FALSE
account.bank.statement	Bank Statement	Base Object	FALSE
mrp.bom	Bill of Material	Base Object	FALSE
blog.blog	Blog	Base Object	FALSE
blog.post	Blog Post	Base Object	FALSE
res.partner	Contact	Base Object	FALSE
hr.contract	Contract	Base Object	FALSE
hr.department	Department	Base Object	FALSE
mail.channel	Discussion Channel	Base Object	FALSE
mail.thread.cc	Email CC management	Base Object	FALSE
mail.thread	Email Thread	Base Object	FALSE
hr.employee	Employee	Base Object	FALSE
event.event	Event	Base Object	FALSE
event.booth	Event Booth	Base Object	FALSE
event.registration	Event Registration	Base Object	FALSE
hr.expense	Expense	Base Object	FALSE
hr.expense.sheet	Expense Report	Base Object	FALSE
forum.forum	Forum	Base Object	FALSE
forum.post	Forum Post	Base Object	FALSE

Model	Model Description	Type	Transient Model
forum.tag	Forum Tag	Base Object	FALSE
gamification.badge	Gamification Badge	Base Object	FALSE
gamification.challenge	Gamification Challenge	Base Object	FALSE
hr.job	Job Position	Base Object	FALSE
account.journal	Journal	Base Object	FALSE
account.move	Journal Entry	Base Object	FALSE
stock.production.lot	Lot/Serial	Base Object	FALSE
mail.blacklist	Mail Blacklist	Base Object	FALSE
mail.thread.blacklist	Mail Blacklist mixin	Base Object	FALSE
note.note	Note	Base Object	FALSE
account.payment	Payments	Base Object	FALSE
phone.blacklist	Phone Blacklist	Base Object	FALSE
mail.thread.phone	Phone Blacklist Mixin	Base Object	FALSE
account.reconcile.model	Preset to create journal entries during a invoices and payments matching	Base Object	FALSE
product.product	Product	Base Object	FALSE
product.template	Product Template	Base Object	FALSE
mrp.production	Production Order	Base Object	FALSE
purchase.order	Purchase Order	Base Object	FALSE
sale.order	Sales Order	Base Object	FALSE
crm.team	Sales Team	Base Object	FALSE
crm.team.member	Sales Team Member	Base Object	FALSE
stock.scrap	Scrap	Base Object	FALSE
account.account.template	Templates for Accounts	Base Object	FALSE
stock.picking	Transfer	Base Object	FALSE
mrp.unbuild	Unbuild Order	Base Object	FALSE
auth_totp.wizard	2-Factor Setup Wizard	Base Object	TRUE
res.groups	Access Groups	Base Object	FALSE
account.cash.rounding	Account Cash Rounding	Base Object	FALSE
account.chart.template	Account Chart Template	Base Object	FALSE
account.common.report	Account Common Report	Base Object	TRUE
account.group	Account Group	Base Object	FALSE
account.invoice.send	Account Invoice Send	Base Object	TRUE
account.journal.group	Account Journal Group	Base Object	FALSE
report.account.report_journal	Account Journal Report	Base Object	FALSE
account.move.reversal	Account Move Reversal	Base Object	TRUE
account.print.journal	Account Print Journal	Base Object	TRUE
account.account.tag	Account Tag	Base Object	FALSE
account.tax.report	Account Tax Report	Base Object	FALSE
account.tax.report.line	Account Tax Report Line	Base Object	FALSE
account.account.type	Account Type	Base Object	FALSE
account.unreconcile	Account Unreconcile	Base Object	TRUE

Model	Model Description	Type	Transient Model
account.root	Account codes first 2 digits	Base Object	FALSE
report.account.report_invoice_with_payments	Account report with payment lines	Base Object	FALSE
report.account.report_invoice	Account report without payment lines	Base Object	FALSE
account.tour.upload.bill	Account tour upload bill	Base Object	TRUE
account.tour.upload.bill_email_confirm	Account tour upload bill email confirm	Base Object	TRUE
account.fiscal.position.account.template	Accounts Mapping Template of Fiscal Position	Base Object	FALSE
account.fiscal.position.account	Accounts Mapping of Fiscal Position	Base Object	FALSE
account.accrued.orders.wizard	Accrued Orders Wizard	Base Object	TRUE
ir.actions.act_url	Action URL	Base Object	FALSE
ir.actions.act_window	Action Window	Base Object	FALSE
ir.actions.act_window_close	Action Window Close	Base Object	FALSE
ir.actions.act_window.view	Action Window View	Base Object	FALSE
ir.actions.actions	Actions	Base Object	FALSE
mail.activity	Activity	Base Object	FALSE
mail.activity.mixin	Activity Mixin	Base Object	FALSE
mail.activity.type	Activity Type	Base Object	FALSE
mrp.workcenter.tag	Add tag for the workcenter	Base Object	FALSE
format.address.mixin	Address Format	Base Object	FALSE
website.route	All Website Route	Base Object	FALSE
account.analytic.distribution	Analytic Account Distribution	Base Object	FALSE
account.analytic.group	Analytic Categories	Base Object	FALSE
account.analytic.default	Analytic Distribution	Base Object	FALSE
account.analytic.line	Analytic Line	Base Object	FALSE
account.analytic.tag	Analytic Tags	Base Object	FALSE
ir.module.category	Application	Base Object	FALSE
ir.asset	Asset	Base Object	FALSE
web_editor.assets	Assets Utils	Base Object	FALSE
ir.attachment	Attachment	Base Object	FALSE
hr.attendance	Attendance	Base Object	FALSE
hr.attendance.overtime	Attendance Overtime	Base Object	FALSE
hr.attendance.report	Attendance Statistics	Base Object	FALSE
product.attribute.value	Attribute Value	Base Object	FALSE
auth_totp.device	Authentication Device	Base Object	FALSE
ir.autovacuum	Automatic Vacuum	Base Object	FALSE
sequence.mixin	Automatic sequence	Base Object	FALSE
avatar.mixin	Avatar Mixin	Base Object	FALSE
report.mrp.report_bom_structure	BOM Structure Report	Base Object	FALSE

Model	Model Description	Type	Transient Model
stock.backorder.confirmation	Backorder Confirmation	Base Object	TRUE
stock.backorder.confirmation.line	Backorder Confirmation Line	Base Object	TRUE
mrp.production.backorder.line	Backorder Confirmation Line	Base Object	TRUE
res.bank	Bank	Base Object	FALSE
res.partner.bank	Bank Accounts	Base Object	FALSE
account.bank.statement.cashbox	Bank Statement Cashbox	Base Object	FALSE
account.bank.statement.closebalance	Bank Statement Closing Balance	Base Object	TRUE
account.bank.statement.line	Bank Statement Line	Base Object	FALSE
account.setup.bank.manual.config	Bank setup manual config	Base Object	TRUE
barcodes.barcode_events_mixin	Barcode Event Mixin	Base Object	FALSE
barcode.nomenclature	Barcode Nomenclature	Base Object	FALSE
barcode.rule	Barcode Rule	Base Object	FALSE
base	Base	Base Object	FALSE
base_import.import	Base Import	Base Object	TRUE
base_import.mapping	Base Import Mapping	Base Object	FALSE
hr.employee.base	Basic Employee	Base Object	FALSE
mrp.bom.line	Bill of Material Line	Base Object	FALSE
blog.tag	Blog Tag	Base Object	FALSE
blog.tag.category	Blog Tag Category	Base Object	FALSE
board.board	Board	Base Object	FALSE
mrp.bom.byproduct	Byproduct	Base Object	FALSE
crm.tag	CRM Tag	Base Object	FALSE
utm.stage	Campaign Stage	Base Object	FALSE
mail.shortcode	Canned Response / Shortcode	Base Object	FALSE
cash.box.out	Cash Box Out	Base Object	TRUE
account.cashbox.line	CashBox Line	Base Object	FALSE
change.password.wizard	Change Password Wizard	Base Object	TRUE
stock.change.product.qty	Change Product Quantity	Base Object	TRUE
change.production.qty	Change Production Qty	Base Object	TRUE
chat.room	Chat Room	Base Object	FALSE
chat.room.mixin	Chat Room Mixin	Base Object	FALSE
product.label.layout	Choose the sheet layout to print the labels	Base Object	TRUE
ir.actions.client	Client Action	Base Object	FALSE
account.common.journal.report	Common Journal Report	Base Object	TRUE
bus.bus	Communication Bus	Base Object	FALSE
res.company	Companies	Base Object	FALSE
base.document.layout	Company Document Layout	Base Object	TRUE

Model	Model Description	Type	Transient Model
ir.property	Company Property	Base Object	FALSE
res.config	Config	Base Object	TRUE
res.config.installer	Config Installer	Base Object	TRUE
res.config.settings	Config Settings	Base Object	TRUE
ir.actions.todo	Configuration Wizards	Base Object	FALSE
confirm.stock.sms	Confirm Stock SMS	Base Object	TRUE
stock.inventory.conflict	Conflict in Inventory	Base Object	TRUE
hr.contract.type	Contract Type	Base Object	FALSE
hr.payroll.structure.type	Contract Type	Base Object	FALSE
hr.contract.history	Contract history	Base Object	FALSE
res.country	Country	Base Object	FALSE
res.country.group	Country Group	Base Object	FALSE
res.country.state	Country state	Base Object	FALSE
website.cover_properties.mixin	Cover Properties Website Mixin	Base Object	FALSE
account.automatic.entry.wizard	Create Automatic Entries	Base Object	TRUE
wizard.ir.model.menu.create	Create Menu Wizard	Base Object	TRUE
res.currency	Currency	Base Object	FALSE
res.currency.rate	Currency Rate	Base Object	FALSE
ir.ui.view.custom	Custom View	Base Object	FALSE
decimal.precision	Decimal Precision	Base Object	FALSE
ir.default	Default Values	Base Object	FALSE
ir.demo	Demo	Base Object	TRUE
ir.demo_failure.wizard	Demo Failure wizard	Base Object	TRUE
ir.demo_failure	Demo failure	Base Object	TRUE
hr.departure.reason	Departure Reason	Base Object	FALSE
hr.departure.wizard	Departure Wizard	Base Object	TRUE
digest.digest	Digest	Base Object	FALSE
digest.tip	Digest Tips	Base Object	FALSE
mail.resend.cancel	Dismiss notification for resend by model	Base Object	TRUE
snailmail.letter.cancel	Dismiss notification for resend by model	Base Object	TRUE
sms.cancel	Dismiss notification for resend by model	Base Object	TRUE
mail.followers	Document Followers	Base Object	FALSE
website.sale.extra.field	E-Commerce Extra Info Shown on product page	Base Object	FALSE
account.edi.format	EDI format	Base Object	FALSE
registration.editor	Edit Attendee Details on Sales Confirmation	Base Object	TRUE
registration.editor.line	Edit Attendee Line on Sales Confirmation	Base Object	TRUE

Model	Model Description	Type	Transient Model
account.edi.document	Electronic Document for an account.move	Base Object	FALSE
mail.alias	Email Aliases	Base Object	FALSE
mail.alias.mixin	Email Aliases Mixin	Base Object	FALSE
mail.template.preview	Email Template Preview	Base Object	TRUE
mail.template	Email Templates	Base Object	FALSE
mail.compose.message	Email composition wizard	Base Object	TRUE
mail.resend.message	Email resend wizard	Base Object	TRUE
hr.employee.category	Employee Category	Base Object	FALSE
base.enable.profilng.wizard	Enable profiling for some time	Base Object	TRUE
event.mail	Event Automated Mailing	Base Object	FALSE
event.booth.category	Event Booth Category	Base Object	FALSE
event.booth.configurator	Event Booth Configurator	Base Object	TRUE
event.booth.registration	Event Booth Registration	Base Object	FALSE
event.type.booth	Event Booth Template	Base Object	FALSE
event.event.configurator	Event Configurator	Base Object	TRUE
event.stage	Event Stage	Base Object	FALSE
event.tag	Event Tag	Base Object	FALSE
event.tag.category	Event Tag Category	Base Object	FALSE
event.type	Event Template	Base Object	FALSE
event.type.ticket	Event Template Ticket	Base Object	FALSE
event.event.ticket	Event Ticket	Base Object	FALSE
hr.expense.approve.duplicate	Expense Approve Duplicate	Base Object	TRUE
hr.expense.refuse.wizard	Expense Refuse Reason Wizard	Base Object	TRUE
ir.exports	Exports	Base Object	FALSE
ir.exports.line	Exports Line	Base Object	FALSE
ir.model.fields	Fields	Base Object	FALSE
ir.fields.converter	Fields Converter	Base Object	FALSE
ir.model.fields.selection	Fields Selection	Base Object	FALSE
ir.filters	Filters	Base Object	FALSE
account.fiscal.position	Fiscal Position	Base Object	FALSE
snailmail.letter.format.error	Format Error Sending a Snailmail Letter	Base Object	TRUE
account.full.reconcile	Full Reconcile	Base Object	FALSE
gamification.goal	Gamification Goal	Base Object	FALSE
gamification.goal.definition	Gamification Goal Definition	Base Object	FALSE
gamification.goal.wizard	Gamification Goal Wizard	Base Object	TRUE
gamification.badge.user	Gamification User Badge	Base Object	FALSE

Model	Model Description	Type	Transient Model
gamification.badge.user.wizard	Gamification User Badge Wizard	Base Object	TRUE
gamification.challenge.line	Gamification generic goal for challenge	Base Object	FALSE
payment.link.wizard	Generate Sales Payment Link	Base Object	TRUE
base.geocoder	Geo Coder	Base Object	FALSE
base.geo_provider	Geo Provider	Base Object	FALSE
report.account.report_hash_integrity	Get hash integrity result as PDF.	Base Object	FALSE
portal.wizard	Grant Portal Access	Base Object	TRUE
mail.guest	Guest	Base Object	FALSE
ir.http	HTTP Routing	Base Object	FALSE
iap.account	IAP Account	Base Object	FALSE
iap.enrich.api	IAP Lead Enrichment API	Base Object	FALSE
iap.autocomplete.api	IAP Partner Autocomplete API	Base Object	FALSE
mail.ice.server	ICE server	Base Object	FALSE
image.mixin	Image Mixin	Base Object	FALSE
mrp.immediate.production	Immediate Production	Base Object	TRUE
mrp.immediate.production.line	Immediate Production Line	Base Object	TRUE
stock.immediate.transfer	Immediate Transfer	Base Object	TRUE
stock.immediate.transfer.line	Immediate Transfer Line	Base Object	TRUE
fetchmail.server	Incoming Mail Server	Base Object	FALSE
account.incoterms	Incoterms	Base Object	FALSE
res.partner.industry	Industry	Base Object	FALSE
base.language.install	Install Language	Base Object	TRUE
stock.inventory.adjustment.name	Inventory Adjustment Reference / Reason	Base Object	TRUE
stock.inventory.warning	Inventory Adjustment Warning	Base Object	TRUE
stock.location	Inventory Locations	Base Object	FALSE
stock.location.route	Inventory Routes	Base Object	FALSE
mail.wizard.invite	Invite wizard	Base Object	TRUE
account.invoice.report	Invoices Statistics	Base Object	FALSE
account.move.line	Journal Item	Base Object	FALSE
base.language.export	Language Export	Base Object	TRUE
base.language.import	Language Import	Base Object	TRUE
res.lang	Languages	Base Object	FALSE
mrp.consumption.warning.line	Line of issue consumption	Base Object	TRUE
mail.channel.partner	Listeners of a Channel	Base Object	FALSE
im_livechat.channel	Livechat Channel	Base Object	FALSE
im_livechat.channel.rule	Livechat Channel Rules	Base Object	FALSE
im_livechat.report.channel	Livechat Support Channel Report	Base Object	FALSE

Model	Model Description	Type	Transient Model
im_livechat.report.operator	Livechat Support Operator Report	Base Object	FALSE
ir.logging	Logging	Base Object	FALSE
mrp.workcenter.productivity.loss.type	MRP Workorder productivity losses	Base Object	FALSE
mail.bot	Mail Bot	Base Object	FALSE
mail.composer.mixin	Mail Composer Mixin	Base Object	FALSE
mail.channel.rtc.session	Mail RTC session	Base Object	FALSE
mail.render.mixin	Mail Render Mixin	Base Object	FALSE
event.type.mail	Mail Scheduling on Event Category	Base Object	FALSE
ir.mail_server	Mail Server	Base Object	FALSE
mail.tracking.value	Mail Tracking Value	Base Object	FALSE
ir.ui.menu	Menu	Base Object	FALSE
base.partner.merge.line	Merge Partner Line	Base Object	TRUE
base.partner.merge.automatic.wizard	Merge Partner Wizard	Base Object	TRUE
mail.message	Message	Base Object	FALSE
mail.notification	Message Notifications	Base Object	FALSE
mail.message.reaction	Message Reaction	Base Object	FALSE
mail.message.subtype	Message subtypes	Base Object	FALSE
stock.warehouse.orderpoint	Minimum Inventory Rule	Base Object	FALSE
ir.model.access	Model Access	Base Object	FALSE
ir.model.constraint	Model Constraint	Base Object	FALSE
ir.model.data	Model Data	Base Object	FALSE
ir.model	Models	Base Object	FALSE
ir.module.module	Module	Base Object	FALSE
report.base.report_irmodulereference	Module Reference Report (base)	Base Object	FALSE
base.module.uninstall	Module Uninstall	Base Object	TRUE
ir.module.module.dependency	Module dependency	Base Object	FALSE
ir.module.module.exclusion	Module exclusion	Base Object	FALSE
website.multi.mixin	Multi Website Mixin	Base Object	FALSE
website.published.multi.mixin	Multi Website Published Mixin	Base Object	FALSE
note.stage	Note Stage	Base Object	FALSE
note.tag	Note Tag	Base Object	FALSE
account.financial.year.op	Opening Balance of Financial Year	Base Object	TRUE
mail.mail	Outgoing Mails	Base Object	FALSE
sms.sms	Outgoing SMS	Base Object	FALSE
stock.quant.package	Packages	Base Object	FALSE
website.page	Page	Base Object	FALSE
report.paperformat	Paper Format Config	Base Object	FALSE

Model	Model Description	Type	Transient Model
account.partial.reconcile	Partial Reconcile	Base Object	FALSE
res.partner.autocomplete.sync	Partner Autocomplete Sync	Base Object	FALSE
res.partner.category	Partner Tags	Base Object	FALSE
res.partner.title	Partner Title	Base Object	FALSE
account.reconcile.model.partner.mapping	Partner mapping for reconciliation models	Base Object	FALSE
mail.resend.partner	Partner with additional information for mail resend	Base Object	TRUE
res.users.identitycheck	Password Check Wizard	Base Object	TRUE
payment.acquirer	Payment Acquirer	Base Object	FALSE
payment.icon	Payment Icon	Base Object	FALSE
account.payment.method.line	Payment Methods	Base Object	FALSE
account.payment.method	Payment Methods	Base Object	FALSE
payment.refund.wizard	Payment Refund Wizard	Base Object	TRUE
account.payment.term	Payment Terms	Base Object	FALSE
account.payment.term.line	Payment Terms Line	Base Object	FALSE
payment.token	Payment Token	Base Object	FALSE
payment.transaction	Payment Transaction	Base Object	FALSE
payment.acquirer.onboarding.wizard	Payment acquire onboarding wizard	Base Object	TRUE
stock.picking.type	Picking Type	Base Object	FALSE
hr.plan.wizard	Plan Wizard	Base Object	TRUE
hr.plan.activity.type	Plan activity type	Base Object	FALSE
portal.mixin	Portal Mixin	Base Object	FALSE
portal.share	Portal Sharing	Base Object	TRUE
portal.wizard.user	Portal User Config	Base Object	TRUE
forum.post.reason	Post Closing Reason	Base Object	FALSE
forum.post.vote	Post Vote	Base Object	FALSE
product.pricelist	Pricelist	Base Object	FALSE
report.product.report_pricelist	Pricelist Report	Base Object	FALSE
product.pricelist.item	Pricelist Rule	Base Object	FALSE
procurement.group	Procurement Group	Base Object	FALSE
product.attribute	Product Attribute	Base Object	FALSE
product.attribute.custom.value	Product Attribute Custom Value	Base Object	FALSE
product.category	Product Category	Base Object	FALSE
product.image	Product Image	Base Object	FALSE
report.product.report_producttemplatelabel	Product Label Report	Base Object	FALSE
report.stock.label_product_product_view	Product Label Report	Base Object	FALSE

Model	Model Description	Type	Transient Model
report.product.report_p roducttemplatelabel_d ymo	Product Label Report	Base Object	FALSE
stock.move.line	Product Moves (Stock Move Line)	Base Object	FALSE
product.packaging	Product Packaging	Base Object	FALSE
product.replenish	Product Replenish	Base Object	TRUE
product.template.attrib ute.exclusion	Product Template Attribute Exclusion	Base Object	FALSE
product.template.attrib ute.line	Product Template Attribute Line	Base Object	FALSE
product.template.attrib ute.value	Product Template Attribute Value	Base Object	FALSE
uom.uom	Product Unit of Measure	Base Object	FALSE
uom.category	Product UoM Categories	Base Object	FALSE
product.ribbon	Product ribbon	Base Object	FALSE
mrp.document	Production Document	Base Object	FALSE
ir.profile	Profiling results	Base Object	FALSE
report.sale.report_sale proforma	Proforma Report	Base Object	FALSE
hr.employee.public	Public Employee	Base Object	FALSE
publisher_warranty.co ntract	Publisher Warranty Contract	Base Object	FALSE
purchase.order.line	Purchase Order Line	Base Object	FALSE
purchase.report	Purchase Report	Base Object	FALSE
purchase.bill.union	Purchases & Bills Union	Base Object	FALSE
stock.putaway.rule	Putaway Rule	Base Object	FALSE
stock.quant	Quants	Base Object	FALSE
sale.order.template	Quotation Template	Base Object	FALSE
sale.order.template.lin e	Quotation Template Line	Base Object	FALSE
sale.order.template.opt ion	Quotation Template Option	Base Object	FALSE
ir.qweb	Qweb	Base Object	FALSE
ir.qweb.field	Qweb Field	Base Object	FALSE
ir.qweb.field.barcode	Qweb Field Barcode	Base Object	FALSE
ir.qweb.field.contact	Qweb Field Contact	Base Object	FALSE
ir.qweb.field.date	Qweb Field Date	Base Object	FALSE
ir.qweb.field.datetime	Qweb Field Datetime	Base Object	FALSE
ir.qweb.field.duration	Qweb Field Duration	Base Object	FALSE
ir.qweb.field.float	Qweb Field Float	Base Object	FALSE
ir.qweb.field.float_time	Qweb Field Float Time	Base Object	FALSE
ir.qweb.field.html	Qweb Field HTML	Base Object	FALSE
ir.qweb.field.image	Qweb Field Image	Base Object	FALSE
ir.qweb.field.image_url	Qweb Field Image	Base Object	FALSE
ir.qweb.field.integer	Qweb Field Integer	Base Object	FALSE
ir.qweb.field.many2one	Qweb Field Many to One	Base Object	FALSE
ir.qweb.field.monetary	Qweb Field Monetary	Base Object	FALSE

Model	Model Description	Type	Transient Model
ir.qweb.field.relative	Qweb Field Relative	Base Object	FALSE
ir.qweb.field.selection	Qweb Field Selection	Base Object	FALSE
ir.qweb.field.text	Qweb Field Text	Base Object	FALSE
ir.qweb.field.qweb	Qweb Field qweb	Base Object	FALSE
ir.qweb.field.many2many	Qweb field many2many	Base Object	FALSE
gamification.karma.rank	Rank based on karma	Base Object	FALSE
rating.rating	Rating	Base Object	FALSE
rating.mixin	Rating Mixin	Base Object	FALSE
rating.parent.mixin	Rating Parent Mixin	Base Object	FALSE
account.reconcile.model.line.template	Reconcile Model Line Template	Base Object	FALSE
account.reconcile.model.template	Reconcile Model Template	Base Object	FALSE
ir.rule	Record Rule	Base Object	FALSE
account.payment.register	Register Payment	Base Object	TRUE
event.mail.registration	Registration Mail Scheduler	Base Object	FALSE
ir.model.relation	Relation Model	Base Object	FALSE
account.resequence.wizard	Remake the sequence of Journal Entries.	Base Object	TRUE
product.removal	Removal Strategy	Base Object	FALSE
mail.blacklist.remove	Remove email from blacklist wizard	Base Object	TRUE
phone.blacklist.remove	Remove phone from blacklist	Base Object	TRUE
ir.actions.report	Report Action	Base Object	FALSE
report.layout	Report Layout	Base Object	FALSE
sms.resend.recipient	Resend Notification	Base Object	TRUE
reset.view.arch.wizard	Reset View Architecture Wizard	Base Object	TRUE
resource.mixin	Resource Mixin	Base Object	FALSE
resource.calendar.leaves	Resource Time Off Detail	Base Object	FALSE
resource.calendar	Resource Working Time	Base Object	FALSE
resource.resource	Resources	Base Object	FALSE
stock.return.picking	Return Picking	Base Object	TRUE
stock.return.picking.line	Return Picking Line	Base Object	TRUE
website.robots	Robots.txt Editor	Base Object	TRUE
account.reconcile.model.line	Rules for the reconciliation model	Base Object	FALSE
stock.scheduler.compute	Run Scheduler Manually	Base Object	TRUE
website.seo.metadata	SEO metadata	Base Object	FALSE
sms.api	SMS API	Base Object	FALSE
sms.resend	SMS Resend	Base Object	TRUE
sms.template.preview	SMS Template Preview	Base Object	TRUE
sms.template	SMS Templates	Base Object	FALSE
sale.order.option	Sale Options	Base Object	FALSE

Model	Model Description	Type	Transient Model
sale.payment.acquirer.onboarding.wizard	Sale Payment acquire onboarding wizard	Base Object	TRUE
sale.advance.payment.inv	Sales Advance Payment Invoice	Base Object	TRUE
sale.report	Sales Analysis Report	Base Object	FALSE
sale.order.cancel	Sales Order Cancel	Base Object	TRUE
sale.order.line	Sales Order Line	Base Object	FALSE
report.all.channels.sales	Sales by Channel (All in One)	Base Object	FALSE
ir.cron	Scheduled Actions	Base Object	FALSE
sms.composer	Send SMS Wizard	Base Object	TRUE
ir.sequence	Sequence	Base Object	FALSE
ir.sequence.date_range	Sequence Date Range	Base Object	FALSE
ir.actions.server	Server Action	Base Object	FALSE
ir.server.object.lines	Server Action value mapping	Base Object	FALSE
snailmail.confirm	Snailmail Confirm	Base Object	FALSE
snailmail.confirm.invoice	Snailmail Confirm Invoice	Base Object	TRUE
snailmail.letter	Snailmail Letter	Base Object	FALSE
stock.orderpoint.snooze	Snooze Orderpoint	Base Object	TRUE
stock.assign.serial	Stock Assign Serial Numbers	Base Object	TRUE
stock.move	Stock Move	Base Object	FALSE
stock.package.destination	Stock Package Destination	Base Object	TRUE
stock.package_level	Stock Package Level	Base Object	FALSE
stock.quantity.history	Stock Quantity History	Base Object	TRUE
report.stock.quantity	Stock Quantity Report	Base Object	FALSE
report.stock.report_reception	Stock Reception Report	Base Object	FALSE
report.stock.report_product_product_replenishment	Stock Replenishment Report	Base Object	FALSE
report.stock.report_product_template_replenishment	Stock Replenishment Report	Base Object	FALSE
stock.request.count	Stock Request an Inventory Count	Base Object	TRUE
stock.rule	Stock Rule	Base Object	FALSE
stock.rules.report	Stock Rules report	Base Object	TRUE
stock.track.confirmation	Stock Track Confirmation	Base Object	TRUE
stock.track.line	Stock Track Line	Base Object	TRUE
stock.valuation.layer	Stock Valuation Layer	Base Object	FALSE
stock.package.type	Stock package type	Base Object	FALSE
report.stock.report_stock_rule	Stock rule report	Base Object	FALSE
stock.replenishment.info	Stock supplier replenishment information	Base Object	TRUE

Model	Model Description	Type	Transient Model
stock.storage.category	Storage Category	Base Object	FALSE
stock.storage.category.capacity	Storage Category Capacity	Base Object	FALSE
product.supplierinfo	Supplier Pricelist	Base Object	FALSE
ir.config_parameter	System Parameter	Base Object	FALSE
account.tax	Tax	Base Object	FALSE
tax.adjustments.wizard	Tax Adjustments Wizard	Base Object	TRUE
account.tax.group	Tax Group	Base Object	FALSE
account.fiscal.position.tax.template	Tax Mapping Template of Fiscal Position	Base Object	FALSE
account.fiscal.position.tax	Tax Mapping of Fiscal Position	Base Object	FALSE
account.tax.repartition.line	Tax Repartition Line	Base Object	FALSE
account.tax.repartition.line.template	Tax Repartition Line Template	Base Object	FALSE
account.tax.carryover.line	Tax carryover line	Base Object	FALSE
account.group.template	Template for Account Groups	Base Object	FALSE
account.fiscal.position.template	Template for Fiscal Position	Base Object	FALSE
account.tax.template	Templates for Taxes	Base Object	FALSE
resource.test	Test Resource Model	Base Object	FALSE
base_import.tests.models.preview	Tests : Base Import Model Preview	Base Object	FALSE
base_import.tests.models.char	Tests : Base Import Model, Character	Base Object	FALSE
base_import.tests.models.char.noreadonly	Tests : Base Import Model, Character No readonly	Base Object	FALSE
base_import.tests.models.char.readonly	Tests : Base Import Model, Character readonly	Base Object	FALSE
base_import.tests.models.char.required	Tests : Base Import Model, Character required	Base Object	FALSE
base_import.tests.models.char.states	Tests : Base Import Model, Character states	Base Object	FALSE
base_import.tests.models.char.stillreadonly	Tests : Base Import Model, Character still readonly	Base Object	FALSE
base_import.tests.models.m2o	Tests : Base Import Model, Many to One	Base Object	FALSE
base_import.tests.models.m2o.related	Tests : Base Import Model, Many to One related	Base Object	FALSE
base_import.tests.models.m2o.required	Tests : Base Import Model, Many to One required	Base Object	FALSE
base_import.tests.models.m2o.required.related	Tests : Base Import Model, Many to One required related	Base Object	FALSE
base_import.tests.models.o2m	Tests : Base Import Model, One to Many	Base Object	FALSE

Model	Model Description	Type	Transient Model
base_import.tests.models.o2m.child	Tests : Base Import Model, One to Many child	Base Object	FALSE
base_import.tests.models.complex	Tests: Base Import Model Complex	Base Object	FALSE
base_import.tests.models.float	Tests: Base Import Model Float	Base Object	FALSE
theme.ir.asset	Theme Asset	Base Object	FALSE
theme.ir.attachment	Theme Attachments	Base Object	FALSE
theme.ir.ui.view	Theme UI View	Base Object	FALSE
theme.utils	Theme Utils	Base Object	FALSE
web_tour.tour	Tours	Base Object	FALSE
stock.traceability.report	Traceability Report	Base Object	TRUE
gamification.karma.tracking	Track Karma Changes	Base Object	FALSE
ir.translation	Translation	Base Object	FALSE
ir.cron.trigger	Triggered actions	Base Object	FALSE
utm.campaign	UTM Campaign	Base Object	FALSE
utm.medium	UTM Medium	Base Object	FALSE
utm.mixin	UTM Mixin	Base Object	FALSE
utm.source	UTM Source	Base Object	FALSE
utm.tag	UTM Tag	Base Object	FALSE
website.base.unit	Unit of Measure for price per unit on eCommerce products.	Base Object	FALSE
_unknown	Unknown	Base Object	FALSE
base.module.update	Update Module	Base Object	TRUE
base.update.translations	Update Translations	Base Object	TRUE
snailmail.letter.missing.required.fields	Update address of partner	Base Object	TRUE
base.module.upgrade	Upgrade Module	Base Object	TRUE
bus.presence	User Presence	Base Object	FALSE
res.users.settings	User Settings	Base Object	FALSE
res.users.settings.volumes	User Settings Volumes	Base Object	FALSE
change.password.user	User, Change Password Wizard	Base Object	TRUE
res.users	Users	Base Object	FALSE
res.users.log	Users Log	Base Object	FALSE
validate.account.move	Validate Account Move	Base Object	TRUE
vendor.delay.report	Vendor Delay Report	Base Object	FALSE
ir.ui.view	View	Base Object	FALSE
website.track	Visited Pages	Base Object	FALSE
stock.warehouse	Warehouse	Base Object	FALSE
stock.warn.insufficient.qty	Warn Insufficient Quantity	Base Object	FALSE
stock.warn.insufficient.qty.scrap	Warn Insufficient Scrap Quantity	Base Object	TRUE
stock.warn.insufficient.qty.unbuild	Warn Insufficient Unbuild Quantity	Base Object	TRUE

Model	Model Description	Type	Transient Model
web_editor.converter.test.sub	Web Editor Converter Subtest	Base Object	FALSE
web_editor.converter.test	Web Editor Converter Test	Base Object	FALSE
website	Website	Base Object	FALSE
website.configurator.feature	Website Configurator Feature	Base Object	FALSE
website.menu	Website Menu	Base Object	FALSE
website.sale.payment.acquirer.onboarding.wizard	Website Payment acquire onboarding wizard	Base Object	TRUE
product.public.category	Website Product Category	Base Object	FALSE
website.published.mixin	Website Published Mixin	Base Object	FALSE
website.searchable.mixin	Website Searchable Mixin	Base Object	FALSE
website.snippet.filter	Website Snippet Filter	Base Object	FALSE
theme.website.menu	Website Theme Menu	Base Object	FALSE
theme.website.page	Website Theme Page	Base Object	FALSE
website.visitor	Website Visitor	Base Object	FALSE
website.rewrite	Website rewrite	Base Object	FALSE
mrp.consumption.warning	Wizard in case of consumption in warning/strict and more component has been used for a MO (related to the bom)	Base Object	TRUE
stock.valuation.layer.revaluation	Wizard model to reevaluate a stock inventory for a product	Base Object	TRUE
mrp.production.backorder	Wizard to mark as done or create back order	Base Object	TRUE
mrp.workcenter	Work Center	Base Object	FALSE
mrp.routing.workcenter	Work Center Usage	Base Object	FALSE
resource.calendar.attendance	Work Detail	Base Object	FALSE
hr.work.location	Work Location	Base Object	FALSE
mrp.workorder	Work Order	Base Object	FALSE
mrp.workcenter.productivity	Workcenter Productivity Log	Base Object	FALSE
mrp.workcenter.productivity.loss	Workcenter Productivity Losses	Base Object	FALSE
hr.plan	plan	Base Object	FALSE
res.users.apikeys	res.users.apikeys	Base Object	FALSE
res.users.apikeys.description	res.users.apikeys.description	Base Object	TRUE
res.users.apikeys.show	res.users.apikeys.show	Base Object	FALSE

Table 6: System Models (ir.model)

Field Name	FALSE	TRUE	Grand Total
binary	170		170

Field Name	FALSE	TRUE	Grand Total
boolean	1247	12	1259
char	1695	80	1775
date	143	11	154
datetime	1373	16	1389
float	343	1	344
html	108		108
integer	1156	10	1166
many2many	338		338
many2one	2303	274	2577
many2one_reference	4	3	7
monetary	121		121
one2many	510		510
reference	10		10
selection	534	24	558
text	187	3	190
Grand Total	10242	434	10676

Table 6: System Field Count by Field Name (ir.model.fields)

E. Implementation

In this section, the significant methodology phases and milestones are explained. Key activities, scope, and management structure are discussed concerning the implementation approach of the project. The official start date was determined by the date the project plan is agreed upon and communicated between the student and the client.

a. Methodology

The IT-facilitated CRPS was deployed using *Rapid Implementation Methodology*. This methodology was designed for IT Best Practices implementation approach. There are four phases in a Rapid Implementation:

Phase 1: Project Preparation (3 Weeks)

The goal of this phase was to review the detailed project plan, procedures, and staffing based on the detailed scope discussions and agreements of the pre-implementation phases (IS295a activities) and to perform installation of the development environment.

Deliverable	Responsible Group
Project Plan Sign-Off	Project Team
Design Sign-Off	Villegas Organiks
Project environment Established	Student
Project Core Team Identified	Student

Project Kick-off Meeting Conducted	Project Team
Hardware Ready (Laptop PC Server)	Student
Software Installed (DEV)	Student

Table 7: Phase 1 Project Preparation Deliverables

Phase 2: Realization (2 Weeks)

The purpose of this Phase was to configure the “Best Practices – Out-of-the-box”, test load data from the existing sources, unit test business process in scope, install the test and production systems, develop plan for production support, establish authorizations, and prepare for User Acceptance Testing (UAT) and Roll-out.

Deliverable	Responsible Group
Odoo ERP out-of-the-box configurations	Student
Data cleansing	Villegas Organiks Key Users
Documented Business Process Guides	Student
Built Production Environment	Student
Confirmed Test Plans	Project Team
Conducted Initial hands-on training and evaluation of Best Practice	Student
Confirmed Cut-Over Plan	Project Team

Table 8: Phase 2 Realization Deliverables

Phase 3: Final Preparation (1 Week)

During this Phase the Project Team completed the final preparation for Go-Live. This includes performing UAT, trial testing, system management and cut-over activities. During the successful completion of this Phase, the system is ready, the legacy data has been migrated and Villegas Organiks is ready to run the CRPS live in the Odoo ERP system.

Deliverable	Responsible Group
Trained Key Users	Student
Tested Production System (Trial testing, VA&PT, Backup, etc.)	Student, Key Users
Prepared production system (Configuration transported and crop production protocols for 2022 was converted)	Student
Established Help Desk	Project Team

Table 9: Phase 3 Final Preparation Deliverables

Phase 4: Go-Live and Support (1 Week)

The purpose of this Phase was to move to a live production operation. During this Phase, the Villegas Organiks maintained the support of the

delivered processes to the student. The Project Team monitored system transactions and optimized overall system performance.

Deliverable	Responsible Group
Live Production System	Project Team
Completed Hyper Care Support	Student
Project Closed	Project Team

Table 10: Phase 4 Go Live Deliverables

b. In-Scope Activities

Project activities conducted and performed by the student are as follows:

- (1) Planning, designing, development, testing, and implementation of the technology based CRPS.
- (2) Provided Project Plan outlining the finalized methodology and project timeline.
- (3) Carried out a review and assessment of Villegas Organiks website contents and existing crop rotation planning process workflow and production protocols.
- (4) Undertaken a review and detailed technical design of solution based on the current Villegas Organiks process and procedures.
- (5) Provided the following project documentation:
 - Business Blueprint Document
 - Functional and Technical Specifications
 - Stakeholders Map Matrix with Needs/Requirements analysis
 - Solution Concept Diagram
 - Wireframes and Prototypes
 - User and System Admin Manuals
- (6) Provided User Acceptance Testing (UAT) support, lead the testing execution and collaboration within participants to ensure the issues are resolved accordingly.
- (7) Implemented and managed the cleansing and migration of contents from the current data source to the IT-facilitated CRPS.
- (8) Provided training modules and training for the end-users and system administrators.

c. High-Level Project Schedule

Project Start Date:	10/18/2021	*Workdays include Weekends & Holidays				
Overall Progress:	100%					
Milestone description	Category	Assigned to	Progress	Planned Start	Week	Days
Evaluation			100%			

Project Start Date:	10/18/2021	*Workdays include Weekends & Holidays				
Overall Progress:	100%					
Milestone description	Category	Assigned to	Progress	Planned Start	Week	Days
Project Preparation	Goal	Client & Student	100%	10/18/2021	1	5
Gap Analysis and Documentation	Goal	Student	100%	10/23/2021	1	7
Functional Workshops	Goal	Client & Student	100%	10/30/2021	2	2
Design Sign-Off	Goal	Client	100%	11/1/2021	3	1
Evaluation Completed	Milestone	Student	100%	11/1/2021	3	1
Implementation			100%			
System Installation	Goal	Student	100%	11/2/2021	3	2
Task Assignment	Goal	Client & Student	100%	11/4/2021	3	4
Project Team Training	Goal	Client & Student	100%	11/8/2021	4	2
Kick-off Meeting	Goal	Client & Student	100%	11/10/2021	4	1
Realization	Goal	Client & Student	100%	11/11/2021	4	12
Training	Goal	Student	100%	11/23/2021	6	3
Testing	Goal	Client	100%	11/26/2021	6	2
Final Preparation	Goal	Client & Student	100%	11/28/2021	6	1
Cut-Over Planning	Goal	Client & Student	100%	11/29/2021	7	1
Go-Live	Goal	Client & Student	100%	11/30/2021	7	1
Hypercare	Goal	Student	100%	12/1/2021	7	3
Implementation Completed	Milestone	Student	100%	12/4/2021	7	1

Table 11: High-Level Schedule of Activities

The duration of the pilot phase implementation covering the above-mentioned activities and scope were 7 weeks. The table above also shows a high-level representation of important project milestones and tasks.

d. Management Structure and Key Personnel

The key success factor for the pilot implementation of the system was a strong core project team that consists of both operational resources, technical resource, and project team resources working together.

Project Core Team Members

- Villegas Organiks Representatives
- Student

Information System Resource

The student also served as the Information System Analyst and helped the project team members in creating the requirement specifications to work from. The student being the IS Analyst helped the Villegas Organiks key users understand technical limitations such as why certain requirements will not fit. Additionally, the student established the development process and performed the actual system installation and configuration for the establishment of the information system.

The project work execution includes design and architecture, requirements analysis, designing and development, quality assurance, implementation, and overall project management. Aside from the student, the Villegas Organiks allocated the following resources for the development and establishment of the technology-based Crop Rotation Planning System.

- (9) Operations Manager as Project Manager counterpart
- (10) Farm Consultants as Key Users and Key Informants
- (11) Farmers as End-Users
- (12) Other Onsite People as Observants
- (13) Facilities

e. Project Dependencies

No dependency identified. Possible dependencies will be reviewed as the phase 2 of the project progresses.

Chapter IV

Project Assessment

A. User Testing

The student closely coordinated with the Villegas Organiks project team and stakeholders in identifying system improvement and testing of the application to ensure that specifications and features meet the requirements of the crop rotation planning process and procedures, and the accessibility of the farmers.

User testing sessions were facilitated by the student and the Operations Manager, Mr. Joshua Samuel B. Villegas, wherein all users were able to go through and test their relevant module functionalities.

The table below summarizes the activities laid out for this phase of the project.

Responsible Group	Point-of-Contact	Date of Meetings	Summary
Student	Honey Mae A. Samson	November 08, 2021	Presentation of initial version of the CRPS to the Operations Manager. CRPS version 0.1 Filling up of information needed to populate the system data.
Student	Honey Mae A. Samson	November 08, 2021, to November 22, 2021	Evaluation of the system workflow, logic, and persisting bugs. Configuration of the system to address the incorrect data entries and processes.
Student	Honey Mae A. Samson	November 23, 2021	Presentation of the second version of the CRPS to the Villegas Organiks Project Team. CRPS version 1.0
Villegas Organiks	Joshua Samuel B. Villegas	November 26, 2021	User Acceptance Testing (UAT) for the three possible users (Operations Manager, Farm Consultant, and

Responsible Group	Point-of-Contact	Date of Meetings	Summary
			Farmer) to evaluate the overall system in terms of user experience and usability. CRPS version 2.0
Villegas Organiks	Joshua Samuel B. Villegas	November 28, 2021	Trial Testing for selected farmers to check other possible bugs before the pilot implementation.
All	Honey Mae A. Samson	November 30, 2021	Villegas Organiks formally accepted the proposed solution. CRPS version 3.0

Table 12: Summary of User Testing Activities

As presented in the above table, there were four testing sessions happened in this phase. Initially an internal system walkthrough was done after the prototype was created. The general aim was to check whether the design presented in the solution generation was achieved by the student or compromises needed to be done. The recommendations from this phase were considered for inclusion in the second version of the prototype.

A system walkthrough with the Villegas Organiks Key Users happened to further evaluate the workflow design for CRPS. The goal was to check whether the process was compatible with the current system in the farm and to populate the details which will be present in the system. This phase also included a check of the parameters to be set in the system. The recommendations for this phase were added to version 1.0 of the prototype.

The third testing that happened was the User Acceptance Testing (UAT)⁶ which focused on the evaluation of usability and user experience. This involved representative farmers and employees as testers. A specific set of the script was given to each tester aiming to pass through the critical customer journey paths. Each of the testers was required to key in their comments and status with regards to the specific task given. After the analysis, version 2.0 for the prototype was furnished.

To support the findings for the UAT, trial testing was done. Few farmers were selected and invited to test version 2.0 of the system to determine whether there were still controls that needed to be fixed before the pilot implementation. The

⁶ UAT Results are attached as Annex

difference of the trial testing from the UAT is that this round of testing was free-scripted and therefore potentially evaluated uncontrolled variables. The result of this testing was considered for the release version of the CRPS.

Lastly – and the on-going test – is the pilot implementation. The main agenda of the pilot is to check whether the system will hold on to its natural setting once fully rolled out and to stress test it based on the number of crop productions scheduled. More so, affiliated workflows from the CRPS (i.e., setup in the sales ordering process, website content management, etc.) are to be tested as well. The outputs from this testing will be considered for the second phase of the CRPS – the version ready for full implementation.

Test Result and Quick Feedback

UAT Status: 100%
 Planned Days: 2
 Actual Days: 2

There were three different actors in the testing process, each with different roles. First, the system administrator was tasked to set up the system landscape and create users. The Operations Manager was responsible for creating a crop rotation plan, viewing the crop operations, and generating reports. Lastly, the farmer was responsible for updating the status of the crop plan and operations.

All actors performed the testing for system logging in and our test case, as well as system navigation.

Test Item	Actor/s	Tester/s
System Access and System Navigation	All Actors	Joshua Villegas Berni Mara Christine Baladad
System Administration	System Administrator	Joshua Villegas
System Transactions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Inventory Module ▪ Manufacturing Module 	Farmer, Operations Manager	Joshua Villegas Berni

Table 13: User Testing Items and Actors⁷

During the UAT sessions, the primary issue that was identified is the limitations on instant technology absorption. It was also highlighted that there’s a need to approach the problem on the technological capabilities of the users. It was

⁷ UAT Scripts are attached as Annex

recommended by the Operations Manager to develop strategies to address those who are not technically predisposed (such as Farmers) to the online interface. Additional knowledge transfer and orientation should be pursued.

An essential part of all UAT sessions is a consultation process to gather feedback, suggestions, and other insights. These are noted below:

- (1) Changing the system's home page from 'Discuss' module to 'Dashboard' module.
- (2) Use coaching as the primary means for learning and development, given the small number of staff and the uniqueness of services and IT platforms used.
- (3) Design and implement a daily system performance monitoring to collect and review data on a regular basis to determine progress, anticipate needs, and make necessary adjustments to personnel or system processes.
- (4) Advise and plan procurement of technology hardware such as new desktop units, printers, kiosks, etc.

As the exit criteria were met and satisfied, and assessment of changes was concluded, version 2.0 for the prototype was furnished.

Test Metrics

No of test scripts: 3

No. of test items: 22

No. of test executed: 22

- Passed: 21
- Failed: 1
- No Tested: 0

No. of defects identified and their status and severity:

Status	Critical	Major	Minor	Cosmetic	Total
Closed	0	0	1	1	2
Open	0	0	0	0	0
					2

Out of Scope

The following functionalities were not tested as they are not specified in the requirement specifications and/or are not applicable:

- (1) Hardware Interfaces
- (2) Database Logics
- (3) System Interfaces
- (4) Performance Testing

Test Deliverable

The following were the expected deliverables from the testing process:

Deliverable	Responsible Group	Point-of-Contact
Test Plan	Student	Honey Mae A. Samson
UAT Test Scenarios and Test Cases with expected and actual results	Student	Honey Mae A. Samson
List of Defects	Student	Honey Mae A. Samson

Table 14: User Testing Deliverables

Test Tasks

- (1) The student provided the test environment.
- (2) The student handled all defects/issues raised by the testers.
- (3) The student documented and communicated problems encountered during testing to other users, and resolved problems identified during the tests.
- (4) The student provided the test plan and test scenario design documents.
- (5) The student provided the test scripts and test data executed by the UAT participants.
- (6) The student provided the test cases and procedures as detailed in the test scenario design.
- (7) The Villegas Organiks participants executed the test scenarios using the test document prepared as inputs and ensured that the final outcomes of the tests are passing.
- (8) The Villegas Organiks participants signed-off all test cases by signing the completed test worksheets.

Item Pass/Fail Criteria

- (1) Each tester has assigned test cases.
- (2) Each tester performed step-by-step execution and updated the test status. The tester wrote Passed or Failed for each step on the test script.
- (3) The tester raised the identified defects/bugs to the student with appropriate screenshots of the issue.
- (4) The student gathered and documented all defects/issues encountered by testers.
- (5) The process was repeated until all test cases were executed fully with Pass/Fail status.
- (6) Final sign-off or acceptance was followed.

B. Security Testing

Vulnerability Assessment and Penetration Testing (VA&PT) was performed to provide the student and the Villegas Organiks farm visibility of the application's security weaknesses and provide them guidance on how to address the identified risks.

Security Process Information

VA&PT Tool Used: OWASP ZAP version 2.11.1

VA&PT Execution Date: December 30, 2021

VA&PT Target IP/URL: http://localhost:8069/ HTTP/1.1 (application is locally deployed; mirror copy of the production environment)

User-Agent: Mozilla/5.0 (Windows NT 10.0; Win64; x64; rv:92.0) Gecko/20100101 Firefox/92.0

Pragma: no-cache

Cache-Control: no-cache

ZAP Report

The below table show the number of alerts for each level of risk and confidence included in the scanning report.⁸

		Confidence				Total
		User Confirmed	High	Medium	Low	
Risk	High	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	20 (1.8%)	0 (0.0%)	20 (1.8%)
	Medium	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	156 (13.7%)	0 (0.0%)	156 (13.7%)
	Low	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	676 (59.4%)	10 (0.9%)	686 (60.3%)
	Informational	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	276 (24.3%)	276 (24.3%)
	Total	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	852 (74.9%)	286 (25.1%)	1138 (100%)

Figure 7: ZAP Scanning Report on alerts count for each level of risk and confidence

Table 14 shows the number of alerts of each alert type, together with the alert type's risk level, and recommendation of the student (possible inclusion in the Phase 2 of the project).

⁸ ZAP Scanning Report

Alert type	Risk	Count	Recommendation / Proposed Remediation Activity by the Student
Cross Site Scripting (Reflected)	High	10 (0.9%)	Non-qualifying vulnerability as XSS vulnerabilities works only in unsupported/deprecated browsers or requiring relaxed security settings.
SQL Injection	High	10 (0.9%)	Email Odoo's security team at security@odoo.com to report and share the applications security weaknesses.
.htaccess Information Leak	Medium	32 (2.8%)	Email Odoo's security team at security@odoo.com to report and share the applications security weaknesses.
Vulnerable JS Library	Medium	1 (0.1%)	Email Odoo's security team at security@odoo.com to report and share the applications security weaknesses.
X-Frame-Options Header Not Set	Medium	123 (10.8%)	Ensure that X-Frame-Options is set to DENY.
Absence of Anti-CSRF Tokens	Low	109 (9.6%)	No plausible attack + not preventable
Application Error Disclosure	Low	3 (0.3%)	Email Odoo's security team at security@odoo.com to report and share the applications security weaknesses.
Cookie No HttpOnly Flag	Low	76 (6.7%)	Modify cookie attributes to incorporate "httponly" and "SameSite" flags. Set the SameSite flag to SameSite=Strict
Cookie without SameSite Attribute	Low	338 (29.7%)	
Information Disclosure - Debug Error Messages	Low	3 (0.3%)	Email Odoo's security team at security@odoo.com to report and share the applications security weaknesses.
Timestamp Disclosure - Unix	Low	10 (0.9%)	Email Odoo's security team at security@odoo.com to report and share the applications security weaknesses.
X-Content-Type-Options Header Missing	Low	147 (12.9%)	Ensure that the web server, application server, load balancer, etc. is configured to suppress "X-Powered-By" headers.
Information Disclosure - Suspicious Comments	Informational	13 (1.1%)	Email Odoo's security team at security@odoo.com to report and share the applications security weaknesses.
Loosely Scoped Cookie	Informational	263 (23.1%)	No plausible attack + not preventable

Table 15: ZAP Scanning Report on number of alerts of each alert type

Overall Security Risk Assessment

Risk Approach: Mitigate
Actions to be taken:
(1) The student, as the technical consultant of the Villegas Organiks farm, will be responsible for monitoring the risks and notifying all concerned user groups via email or SMS when a trigger occurs.
(2) The student will coordinate all the security findings to the Odoo provider to assess and remediate them.

(3) The student will be responsible for overseeing risk activities and ensuring the mitigation plan is initiated.
Mitigation/Contingency Plan:
(1) The production environment is not currently expose to the internet; it can only be accessed via the local network of the Villegas Organiks farm.
(2) The production environment has a registration and logging in process to ensure that only authenticated users will be able to access the system.
(3) Continue to monitor the production environment until actions can be taken.

Table 16: CRPS Overall Security Risk Assessment

Chapter V

Discussions

Pilot implementation has been ongoing for eleven weeks, as of writing. The pilot implementation highlighted positive experiences and encouragement for implementers and for the student, as exhibited in the following:

- 1) Presence of and close coordination established between the Villegas Organiks Project Team and the student.
- 2) Immediate and positive feedback received from the farmers and operations manager during and after the orientation, and their engagement through the online collaboration group.
- 3) Initiatives and active engagement of key implementers in the pilot run. All operations managers and farm consultants have attended orientations of the farmers and advocated the use of the system by discussing its benefits not only to the Villegas Organiks farmers, but also to the representative farmers of the Cooperative.
- 4) Mr. Joshua Samuel B. Villegas, Villegas Organiks Operations Manager, mentions in his message during orientations i.e., that the system offered in Villegas Organiks is just the start. They see it being offered in the whole of members of the Cooperative. It answers the problem of manual crop rotation planning and farm management and uses technology and innovation to make service access safer and easier for the farmers and farm owners.
- 5) This was echoed by the Farm Owner, Mr. Pablito M. Villegas, and he solicited the support of the Farm Consultants and Sr. Farmers. He said that the successful pilot of CRPS will pave the way for the use of this innovation as the best practice and model to replicate it in other agriculture service sectors in the country.

Figure 8 & 9: Crop Production Protocols Data Gathering

The results of and learnings from the pilot implementation will be used to further improve and refine the system as the student prepares for the handover of the CRPS to Villegas Organiks. The processes for additional functionalities such as Ordering

process, Invoicing process, eCommerce, and eLearning have already been discussed with the Operations Manager and Farm Owner of the Villegas Organiks and is currently being designed for incorporation into the CRPS during expansion.

Project Success Factors

The following project success factors were defined for the project:

Ownership. Visible and management ownership of the project was crucial. Villegas Organiks operations management has been active, and participants were available in the process ensuring that effective decisions take place.

Acceptance. The transition to the web application functionalities involved change in the work environment of both the users and Villegas Organiks management. Building commitment to this change was an important responsibility of both the Villegas Organiks representatives and the student. Strong Organizational Change Management, Communications and Training strategy throughout the entire project were essential.

Scope control. The boundaries and objectives of this implementation have been clearly defined and communicated in the Project Plan document. A rigorous scope management process has also been established as any development outside the agreed scope may threaten the project in terms of quality and/or schedule.

Talent. The quality of the Project Team impacted the quality of the implemented solution. The Villegas Organiks allotted the best, most knowledgeable (in the crop production operations) resources of the organization dedicated to the CRPS Project implementation. They were empowered to resolve key issues in a timely manner and possessed deep knowledge of internal business processes and business objectives.

Communication. Expected benefits, project objectives and project constraints were clearly stated and communicated to all stakeholders, including the student.

Issues resolution. Timely resolution of issues to prevent delays in the implementation plan was also in place.

Communications

The purpose of this section is to outline the overall communication methods and process for sharing project information defined at the onset of the project.

Communication areas specified are as follows:

(1) Meeting Schedules

- (2) Agendas
- (3) Status Reports
- (4) Kickoff Meeting
- (5) Onsite Support
- (6) Communication process to process owners and end-users

Several communication tools were established to ensure a successful collaborative work, these are as follows:

Email (i.e., Gmail, Google Drive) is the primary medium for Project Management Team communication. Files were forwarded and/or shared immediately. All significant electronic project documentation was posted on the collaborative work site.

Private group messaging environments (i.e., Viber, Messenger) worked well as the Project Team members are spread across different geographical locations. Files were shared and conversations were accessed if needed.

Pre-Work Activities

The pre-work plan was undertaken into two activities. The first activity was a briefing with Villegas Organiks employees, which helped them, and the student determine and understand the scope of the project. This was called to clearly define the personal responsibilities for the execution of the project tasks, for supervision of the tasks, and for the documentation of the supervision.

The second activity was Project Stakeholder briefing with the Villegas Organiks project management team and Subject Matter Expert (SME). The objective of this meeting was to discuss the Project Plan and finalize outputs and deliverables of the student for the establishment of the proposed information system.

Both meetings provided additional guarantee of adherence, and interpretation of the Project Plan. These discussions included a process for clarifying roles and expectations, especially for the pilot implementation and moving forward.

Coordination Meetings and Functional Workshops

During the first week of the project, several coordination meetings with farm experts were conducted to present the proposed work plan and strategies of the technical supportive assistance. Online meetings served as the main forum for interaction between groups. These meetings were held to delineate the scope of the engagement and identify other risks and constraints.

The student also closely coordinated with the Villegas Organiks SME to brainstorm, draft, and finalize the system requirements and preparation for pilot implementation.

There were also Ad hoc meetings facilitated to provide clarifications on the proposed work plan and strategies.

These meetings and workshops took place over ten (10) working days between the dates of October 18, 2021, to October 31, 2021.

Meetings and other activities are listed in the table below:

Date	Activity	Remarks
October 18, 2021	Briefing with Villegas Organiks Key Users	Triggered the finalization of the timeline and the work plan
October 19, 2021	Briefing with Villegas Organiks End-Users	
October 20, 2021	Finalize Timeline and Workplan	Draft submitted to the Villegas Organiks team for review and approval
October 21, 2021 to October 22, 2021	Review and Approval Period	Final workplan and timeline
October 23, 2021	Gap Analysis and Documentation	Documentation of the requirements and identification of gaps.
October 30, 2021 to October 31, 2021	Functional Workshops	Reference for functional and technical specifications of the proposed system.

Table 17: Project Meetings and Workshops

System Functionalities Development

From November 1 to 5, 2021, several meetings were conducted among Farm Operators to brainstorm, draft, and finalize the functional and technical specifications document of the proposed information system in preparation for the pilot implementation. These discussions included a process for clarifying roles and expectations, especially for the pilot and moving forward.

To prepare the Villegas Organiks implementers for the pilot phase starting November 2021, the key activities conducted are listed below:

Date	Activity	Remarks
November 1-2, 2021	Continuation of Functional and Technical	Received approval to proceed last November 5, 2021

Date	Activity	Remarks
	Specifications Documentation	
November 1-2, 2021	Conducted Functional and Technical Evaluation	Received approval to proceed last November 5, 2021
November 1, 2021	System Installation	Installation of cloud-based application Odoo and selection of Odoo modules to meet the requirements of the client.
November 4, 2021	Task Assignment	Validation and assignment of process guides to Villegas Organiks operator and farm director.
November 7-8, 2021	Project Team Training	The orientation of selected operators and process owners on the Odoo modules, and discussion on the module functionalities. Data Gathering on the experiences of process owners and other implementers for the pilot implementation.
November 10, 2021	Kick-off Meeting	Sustainability planning workshop to craft a roadmap for the full roll-out and beyond. Change management and communication planning workshop.
November 11, 2021	Realization	Validation of the Villegas Organiks process guides. Validation of draft organizational design which includes the Villegas Organiks Farm Structure and Landscape, competency-based job description, and the results framework using Odoo out-of- the-box features.

Table 18: Project Key Activities

Extension of the Technical Assistance Support

The student serves as the Helpdesk Support to handle inquiries and provide technical assistance in the use of the platform and perform first level problem resolution. Interactions were done through SMS, calls, and emails.

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Website

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Meeting the demand for crop production: the challenge of yield decline in crops grown in short rotations (Bennett et al., 2012)

Bennett, A., Bending, G., Chandler, D., Hilton, S. and Mills, P., 2012. Meeting the demand for crop production: the challenge of yield decline in crops grown in short rotations. Available at: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/21631700/> [Accessed 11 May 2017].

Appendices

A. Complete Program Listing

The Odoo ERP is available in two editions: Odoo Community (open source) and Odoo Enterprise (licensed).

The version used to establish the IT-facilitated Crop Rotation Planning System (CRPS) is the Odoo *Community* version. This edition can be downloaded in the link below:

<https://www.odoo.com/page/download>

Application Installer

Odoo Edition: Community
Community Version: Odoo 15
OS: Windows

Application Sources

Odoo Edition: Community
Community Version: Odoo 15
Source: Sources

Minimum Hardware Requirements

Windows10 Pro or below
core i3 3220 @ 3.3 GHz
4GB of RAM

Installation and Configuration

1. Execute the downloaded file.
Note: On Windows 8 and later you may see a warning titled "Windows protected your PC". Click on More Info and then on Run anyway.
2. Accept the UAC prompt.
3. Go through the various installation steps.
4. Note: Odoo will automatically be started at the end of the installation.

Installation Notes

- TCP or UDP default is set to 8069.
- Most of the files are Copyright (c) 2004-2015 Odoo S.A. Many files also contain contributions from third parties. In this case the original copyright of the contributions can be traced through the history of the source version control system. When that is not the case, the files contain a prominent notice stating the original copyright and applicable license or come with their

own dedicated COPYRIGHT and/or LICENSE file.¹

- For copyright information, please see the COPYRIGHT file. Odoo is published under the GNU LESSER GENERAL PUBLIC LICENSE, Version 3 (LGPLv3).²
- Some external libraries and contributions bundled with Odoo may be published under other GPL-compatible licenses. For these, please refer to the relevant source files and/or license files, in the source code tree.

Access the Odoo Main Computer connected to the same network

1. Add the port 8069 to the windows firewall.
2. Open the Control Panel, go to System and Security, then select Windows Defender Firewall.
3. Click on Advanced Settings.
A new window will open.
4. Right click on Inbound rules and select New Rule.
5. Select Port option and click on next.
6. Add the port no. 8069 (or the new port if the default value is changed).
7. Select Allow the connection.
8. Choose on which networks you are allowing it.

B. System Features Set

Release Information	
Project:	Crop Rotation Planning System
Internal Release Number:	2.0
Process Impact:	A feature set is simply a table of contents for the individual feature descriptions. Much like a test suite, organizing the feature set by priority, functional area, actor, business object, or release can help identify missing, extra, or poorly motivated features early.

Features by Functional Areas

- F-00 Farm Configuration
- F-01 Crop Information Set Up
- F-02 Variety and Trail Set Up
- F-03 Plot Set Up
- F-04 Protocol Set Up
- F-05 Rotation Planner
- F-06 Report Generation
- F-07 Data Integrity

Features Document

¹ Information available in the Source Code – COPYRIGHT file.

² Information is available in the Source Code – LICENSE file.

F-00 Farm Set Up Configuration	
Priority:	Essential
Effort:	Hours
Risk:	Safe
Functional Area(s):	CRPS Admin
Description:	<p>The farm operator can perform the following actions in the system any point in time:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Farm Information Set Up ▪ Users such as Farmers, Farm Owner, Operators ▪ Crop Information and Variety Definition ▪ Plot Setup ▪ Protocol Setup <p>The following information will be recorded easily:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Crop Types ▪ Varieties ▪ Plot Types and Locations ▪ Soil Types and Nutrient Requirements

F-01 Crop Information Set Up	
Priority:	Essential
Effort:	Hours
Risk:	Safe
Functional Area(s):	Farm Operator
Description:	<p>Helps the farm to keep their crop information in one place.</p> <p>The following information will be recorded easily:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Crop Name ▪ Crop Code ▪ Crop Type ▪ Time to Prepare, Sow, Emerge, Transplant, Harvest ▪ Farm Fields and Beds ▪ Greenhouses

F-02 Products and Variety Set Up	
Priority:	Essential
Effort:	Hours
Risk:	Safe
Functional Area(s):	Farm Operator

F-02 Products and Variety Set Up	
Description:	The following information will be recorded in the system: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Product Name ▪ Product Variants ▪ Product Type ▪ Unit of Measure and Conversion Amount ▪ Product Category ▪ Product Quantity ▪ Sales Price and Cost to Produce ▪ Operations and Logistics

F-03 Plot Set Up	
Priority:	Essential
Effort:	Hours
Risk:	Safe
Functional Area(s):	Farm Operator and Farmers
Description:	The following information will be recorded in the system: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Plot Location ▪ Plot Code ▪ Alternative Plots ▪ Set up Time ▪ Cleanup Time

F-04 Crop Production Protocol	
Priority:	Essential
Effort:	Hours
Risk:	Safe
Functional Area(s):	Farm Operator and Farmers
Description:	The farm operator will be able to set up a protocol and work orders before creating a rotation planner.

F-05 Rotation Planning	
Priority:	Essential
Effort:	Hours
Risk:	Safe
Functional Area(s):	Farm Operator and Farmers
Description:	The user will be able to do the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ List of crops planned for each plot ▪ Receive Crop Requests

F-06 Reports Generation	
Priority:	Essential
Effort:	Hours
Risk:	Safe
Functional Area(s):	Farm Owner and Farm Operator
Description:	<p>The manager will be able to generate the following reports:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Crop Rotation Worksheet Summary ▪ Crops by Plot ▪ Available Crop Products ▪ Actual and Forecasted yields

F-07 Data Integrity	
Priority:	Essential
Effort:	Hours
Risk:	Safe
Functional Area(s):	CRPS Admin
Description:	<p>System has a comprehensive audit log that covers all the actions on the system made by all the users. If there is any doubt about a transaction or a sequence of events, you want to know who did what and when, with minimal effort.</p>

C. Software Requirements Specifications

Release Information	
Project:	Crop Rotation Planning System
Internal Release Number:	2.0
Attached Worksheets:	<p>SRS > Use Case Suite</p> <p>SRS > Features Set</p>
Related Documents:	Project Plan
Process Impact:	<p>The SRS precisely defines the software product that will be built. Decisions made in writing the SRS are based on information in the project proposal and use case documents. The SRS sets requirements that must be satisfied by the system design.</p>

Introduction

The project is the design and implementation of an interactive web-based application to organize the crop information, rotation, and scheduling in an easily accessible, centralized database.

The following activities can be performed in Crop Rotation Planner system:

- All crop records are in one place and easily accessible
- Organized records for compliance reporting
- Field and crop identification and histories
- Improved crop and rotation planning
- Farm Set up Configuration
- User and Role Accountability

Use Cases

Crop Rotation Planning System (CRPS) will cover various use cases that are relevant to maintain the users of the system, mapping of user roles, and configuration of farm setup, crop rotation planning, approval, and reports generation.

Details:

- The use case suite lists all use cases in an organized way.
- Actors are described in the user needs document.

Use Case Diagram

This use case diagram is a graphic depiction of the interactions among the elements of Crop Rotation Planning System. It represents methodology used in system analysis to identify, clarify, and organize system requirements of CRPS. The main actors of this system in this Use Case Diagram are System Admin (Super User), System Users such as Operations Manager, Sales Manager, Farmer, and Farm Owner. These actors will perform the different type of use cases such as Farm Set Up, Manage Crops, Manage users and full crop management system operations. Major elements of the UML use case diagram are shown on the picture below:

SRS Fig. 1.0 – Use Case Diagram of Crop Rotation Planner System

Use Case Suite

A use case suite is simply a table of contents for the individual use cases. Much like a test suite, organizing the suite of use cases by priority, functional area, actor, business object, or release can help identify parts of the system that need additional use cases.

CRPS Admin

- UC-00 Configuring Farm Set up
- UC-09 Audit Trail Logs

Farm Operator

- UC-01 Product Creation
- UC-02 Set Up Bill of Materials
- UC-03 Plot and Nursey Set Up
- UC-04 Rotation Planner
- UC-05 Tracking of Crop Production and Crop Requests
- UC-07 Crop Order Fulfillment
- UC-08 Report Generation

Farmer

- UC-05 Tracking of Crop Production and Crop Requests
- UC-06 Transplanting, Watering, Harvesting
- UC-07 Crop Order Fulfillment

Use Cases

Default Aspects of All Use Cases	
Direct Actors:	Users: CRPS Admin, Farm Operator, Farmer, Farm Owner
Pre-requisite:	User is logged in

UC-00: Configuring Farm Set Up	
Summary:	The CRPS Admin can configure the farm set up before creation of rotation planner.
Priority:	Must Have
Use Frequency:	Ad-hoc
Direct Actor(s):	CRPS Admin
Main Success Scenario:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Go to System Settings Menu ▪ Click on the Farm Set Up ▪ Fill-up the Farm Information ▪ Click the Save button ▪ Go to System Settings Menu ▪ Click on the Farm Set Up ▪ Define System User ▪ Click the Save button
Alternative Scenario Extensions:	CRPS Admin can edit/modify or delete saved information.

UC-01: Product Creation	
Summary:	The Farm Operator should be able to populate the master data needed for the Crop Rotation Planning.
Priority:	Must Have
Use Frequency:	Ad-hoc
Direct Actor(s):	Farm Operator
Main Success Scenario:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Go to Inventory Menu ▪ Click on Products ▪ Click Create ▪ Fill-up the Product Information <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Product Name ○ Product Type ○ Product Image ○ Unit of Measure ○ Sales Price ○ Cost ○ Product Category ○ Product Variants

UC-01: Product Creation	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Sales Information ○ Purchase Information ○ Inventory Information ▪ Click the Save button
Alternative Scenario Extensions:	Farm Operator can edit/modify or delete saved information.

UC-02: Set Up Bill of Materials	
Summary:	The Farm Operator should be able to add materials that will be used for the crop production.
Priority:	Must Have
Use Frequency:	Ad-hoc
Direct Actor(s):	Farm Operator
Main Success Scenario:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Go to Inventory Menu ▪ Click on Bill of Materials ▪ Click Create ▪ Fill-up the BoM Information <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Product Name ○ Product Variant ○ Quantity ○ BoM Type ○ Product Components ○ Operation type such as Operation Name, Work Center, Duration ○ Define Manufacturing Readiness and Flexible Consumption ▪ Click the Save button
Alternative Scenario Extensions:	Farm Operator can edit/modify or delete saved information.

UC-03: Plot Set Up	
Summary:	The Farm Operator should be able to create and set up the farm plots and nurseries.
Priority:	Must Have
Use Frequency:	Ad-hoc
Direct Actor(s):	Farm Operator
Main Success Scenario:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Go to Manufacturing Menu ▪ Click on Work Centers ▪ Click Create ▪ Fill-up the WC Information <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Work Center Name (Plot/Field/Nursery) ○ Alternative Work Centers

UC-03: Plot Set Up	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Working Hours ○ Set Up Time ○ Clean Up Time ▪ Click the Save button
Alternative Scenario Extensions:	Farm Operator can edit/modify or delete saved information.

UC-04: Crop Rotation Planning	
Summary:	The Farm Operator should be able to create a plan based on the available crops and crop types.
Priority:	Must Have
Use Frequency:	Ad-hoc
Direct Actor(s):	Farm Operator
Main Success Scenario:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Go to Manufacturing Menu ▪ Click on Manufacturing Order ▪ Click Create ▪ Fill-up the MO Information <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Product Name ○ Quantity to Produce ○ BoM ○ Scheduled Date ○ Responsible Farmer ○ Create Work Orders ▪ Click the Save button
Alternative Scenario Extensions:	Farm Operator can edit/modify or delete saved information.

UC-05: Tracking of Crop Production and Crop Requests	
Summary:	The Farm Operator and/or the Farmer should be able to view all the crop productions and requests.
Priority:	Must Have
Use Frequency:	Ad-hoc
Direct Actor(s):	Farm Operator, Farmers
Main Success Scenario:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Go to Manufacturing Menu ▪ Click on Operations ▪ Click on Manufacturing Orders (Crop Productions)
Alternative Scenario Extensions:	Farm Operator and/or Farmer can generate a summary of the crop orders.

UC-06: Transplanting, Watering, Harvesting	
Summary:	The system should allow farmers monitor the status of the crops.
Priority:	Essential
Use Frequency:	Ad-hoc
Direct Actor(s):	Farmer
Main Success Scenario:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Go to Manufacturing Menu ▪ Click on Operations ▪ Click Work Orders ▪ User will be able to check the status of his/her crop plans.
Alternative Scenario Extensions:	Farmer can generate a summary of the work orders.

UC-07: Crop Order Fulfillment	
Summary:	The system should allow farmers or farm operators see and process all crop orders.
Priority:	Must Have
Use Frequency:	Ad-hoc
Direct Actor(s):	Farmer, Farm Operator
Main Success Scenario:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Go to Sales Menu ▪ Click Orders ▪ Click Work Orders ▪ User will be able to fulfill the scheduled crop orders.
Alternative Scenario Extensions:	Farmer and Farm Operator can generate a summary of the sales orders.

UC-08: Report Generation	
Summary:	The system should allow system users to generate reports based on their record permissions.
Priority:	Should Have
Use Frequency:	Ad-hoc
Direct Actor(s):	All Actors
Main Success Scenario:	User should be able to download a copy of the selected records in csv or excel file format.
Alternative Scenario Extensions:	User should have an option to see the summary of selected records in a list view form, graph, Kanban, calendar, or pivot.

UC-09: Audit Trail	
Summary:	System has a comprehensive audit log that covers all the actions on the system made by all the users.
Priority:	Must Have
Use Frequency:	Ad-hoc
Direct Actor(s):	CRPS Admin
Main Success Scenario:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Go to Audit Trail menu 2. Filter Records by date, user, action 3. System will display records based on the inputted values in the filtering options
Alternative Scenario Extensions:	User should have an option to print the audit logs report.

Functional Requirements

CRPS is accessible through the internet by Villegas Organiks employees. Crop Rotation planning can be created and submitted through the system. The filed planner is routed to the line managers for approval or disapproval. Operations Managers and/or Farmers can generate a summary of their planner.

The following activities can be performed in CRPS:

- Organize crop, yield, and trait information.
- Optimize yields by having the right lists and information.
- Analysis capability to make better decisions and maintain compliance.
- Audit Trail
- Access to Planting and Harvesting Records

Details: The feature set lists all features in an organized way.

Data Management

Entering data in the system is the only possibility to define new record. When defined here, they are subsequently available in other templates for entering related information. The design of the system follows known structures and contains the following actions:

System Object	System Object Functionality
Create	It leads to a prompt window where user can enter a record. SAVE confirms or CANCEL brings user back to the start. After confirmation, a record opens a list table containing the summary of all records inputted with regards to the selected module or process.

System Object	System Object Functionality
Field Selection	In this drop-down menu, user should find previously defined fields for selection. Defined under the Farm Setup module.
Edit Selected Field	When user have selected a previously defined field, click EDIT to get to the editing template.
Save	If user have put in parameters into the template, user can and should save them by clicking this button.
Cancel	Leaves the template and gets user back to the records table after having asked user to save your data.

Non-Functional Requirements

Usability. CRPS shall have simple user interface for effective and enjoyable use. Any user who has experience in using web browsers shall be able to navigate and use the system without extensive training.

Reliability. CRPS shall be highly available 24x7 without any interruptions except for scheduled system maintenance.

Security. To ensure that each component of the system is kept private and safe from access threats, the system is provided with the following security requirements.

- Registration and Logging In/Out mechanism
- Creation of User and Complexity of password
- User Identification and Separation of Roles
- Cryptographic Keys
- Access Control Requirements
 - Administrative Control
 - Physical Controls
 - Technical or Logical Control
- Input Validation Rules
 - Validation of Fields whether they are empty or include banned characters
 - Validation of input sources
 - Notification Messages
 - Displaying previous page
- Web Security Threats
 - SQL Injection
 - Cross Site Scripting (CSS)
 - File System Attacks
 - On Insecure password

Performance and Scalability. All the data in the database is traced and connected to each other using data integrity. It uses various error checking and validation procedures that will highly ensure the completeness, consistent, and accurate data. The three integrity constraints are also implemented in the system. In entity integrity, all the tables must have a primary key which is not null, then referential

integrity which enables a table to another, but one table must have a foreign key which is the primary of the other table, and domain integrity which prevents invalid data to be stored.

Maintainability and Upgradability. The system design and project implementation of CRPS shall be well documented to provide a good reference for maintaining the system. Any change request shall be thoroughly reviewed before implementing. The third-party System Provider shall release functionality upgrades on a quarterly basis. A near-to-zero downtime policy shall be adopted to avoid disruptions.

Supportability and Operability. A knowledge base (help system) shall be created to serve as a guide for troubleshooting any issues related to the usage of the system. Any system bugs shall be escalated by the users to the technical support team. A service level agreement shall be put into place once the system goes live.

Environmental Requirements

A server is required to host the system with the following minimum specifications.

- Odoo version: 15
- Windows10 Pro
- core i3 3220 @ 3.3 GHz
- 4GB of RAM

Data and Import Requirements

The system should have at the very least the following elements:

- Data input
- Data sources, including arrangements for data supply
- Data storage, including hardware and software
- Data processing
- Information output
- Software subsystems to facilitate and integrate data processing and information delivery
- Delivery procedures (for information delivery to the management)
- Software protection system to protect the integrity of data and to provide different levels of access to users
- Structures (organizational, decision making, policy making, etc.)
- All data shall be stored in a standard PostgreSQL RDMS.

D. Odoo Module Design

SRS Fig. 2.0 – Inventory of Products

Reference	Product	Quantity	UoM	Expected Duration	State
Confirmed (1)					
January 2022 (1)					
WHMO/00017	Lettuce Fanfare Green Ice (1 kg)	325.00	kg	17757:55	Confirmed
Done (2)					
November 2021 (1)					
WHMO/00004	Lettuce Fanfare Green Ice (1 kg)	300.00	kg		Done
October 2021 (1)					
WHMO/00003	Lettuce Fanfare Green Ice (1 kg)	300.00	kg		Done
		925.00		NaN:NaN	

SRS Fig. 3.0 – Crop Orders and Production Schedules

Operation	Work Center	Manufacturing Order	Product	Scheduled Start Date	Scheduled End Date	Expected Duration	Real Duration	Status
Field 1 (13 Beds) (12)								
Lettuce Fanfare Green Ice (1 kg) (12)								
Land Preparation (3)								
Land Preparation	Field 1 (13 Beds)	WHMO/00003	Lettuce Fanfare Green Ice (1 kg)	12/30/2021 15:14:22	12/30/2021 15:14:26	00:00	00:04	Finished
Land Preparation	Field 1 (13 Beds)	WHMO/00004	Lettuce Fanfare Green Ice (1 kg)	12/30/2021 15:27:05	12/30/2021 15:27:33	00:00	00:28	Finished
Land Preparation	Field 1 (13 Beds)	WHMO/00017	Lettuce Fanfare Green Ice (1 kg)	01/02/2022 18:05:29	01/03/2022 18:05:28	125:28	00:00	Ready Start Block
Sowing to Emergence (3)								
Sowing	Field 1 (13 Beds)	WHMO/00003	Lettuce Fanfare Green Ice (1 kg)	12/30/2021 15:14:28	12/30/2021 15:14:31	00:00	00:02	Finished
Sowing	Field 1 (13 Beds)	WHMO/00004	Lettuce Fanfare Green Ice (1 kg)	12/30/2021 15:27:39	12/30/2021 15:27:49	00:00	00:10	Finished
Sowing to Emergence	Field 1 (13 Beds)	WHMO/00017	Lettuce Fanfare Green Ice (1 kg)	01/04/2022 18:05:49	01/06/2022 18:06:14	950:26	00:00	Waiting for another WO Start Block
Emergence to Transplanting (3)								
Transplanting	Field 1 (13 Beds)	WHMO/00003	Lettuce Fanfare Green Ice (1 kg)	12/30/2021 15:14:33	12/30/2021 15:14:35	00:00	00:01	Finished
Transplanting	Field 1 (13 Beds)	WHMO/00004	Lettuce Fanfare Green Ice (1 kg)	12/30/2021 15:27:52	12/30/2021 15:27:55	00:00	00:03	Finished
Emergence to Transplanting	Field 1 (13 Beds)	WHMO/00017	Lettuce Fanfare Green Ice (1 kg)	01/07/2022 18:07:24	01/13/2022 18:07:24	7650:00	00:00	Waiting for another WO Start Block
Transplanting to Harvest (3)								
Harvesting	Field 1 (13 Beds)	WHMO/00003	Lettuce Fanfare Green Ice (1 kg)	12/30/2021 15:14:37	12/30/2021 15:14:39	00:00	00:02	Finished
Harvesting	Field 1 (13 Beds)	WHMO/00004	Lettuce Fanfare Green Ice (1 kg)	12/30/2021 15:27:58	12/30/2021 15:28:01	00:00	00:02	Finished
Transplanting to Harvest	Field 1 (13 Beds)	WHMO/00017	Lettuce Fanfare Green Ice (1 kg)	02/01/2022 18:07:59	02/28/2022 16:00:00	8992:01	00:00	Waiting for another WO Start Block
1.2 (Field 1) (0)						00:00	00:00	
1.2 (Field 2) (0)						00:00	00:00	

SRS Fig. 4.0 – Work Orders and Work Schedules

Work Orders 2

Operation	Work Center	Manufacturer	Product	Scheduled Start Date	Expected D...	Real Durat...	Status
Field 1 (13 Beds) (12)							
					17757:55	00:53	
1.2 (Field 1) (0)							
					00:00	00:00	
1.2 (Field 2) (0)							
					00:00	00:00	
1.2 (Field 3) (0)							
					00:00	00:00	
Big Greenhouse (0)							
					00:00	00:00	
Small Greenhouse (0)							
					00:00	00:00	
					17757:55	00:53	

Inventory Overview

- Delivery Orders: 0 To Process
- Returns: 0 To Process
- Crop Productions: 1 To Process
- Resupply Subcontractor: 0 To Process

Products

- Cucumber VR4 Hybrid (1 kg): Price: 100.00 ₪, On hand: 0.00 kg
- Cucumber VR4 Hybrid Seedlings: Price: 0.00 ₪, On hand: 300.00 g
- French Beans Claudine (1 kg): Price: 100.00 ₪, On hand: 0.00 kg
- French Beans Claudine Seedlings: Price: 0.00 ₪, On hand: 300.00 g
- Land Sell Copy (1 sqm): Price: 0.00 ₪
- Lettuce Fanfare Green Ice (1 kg): Price: 120.00 ₪, On hand: 0.00 kg
- Lettuce Fanfare Green Ice Seedlings: Price: 0.00 ₪, On hand: 300.00 g
- Tomato DMax (1 kg): Price: 40.00 ₪, On hand: 0.00 kg
- Tomato DMax Seedlings: Price: 1.00 ₪, On hand: 300.00 g

Manufacturing Orders

Reference	Product	Quantity	UoM	Expected Duration	State
WHMO/00017	Lettuce Fanfare Green Ice (1 kg)	325.00	kg	17757:55	Confirmed
WHMO/00004	Lettuce Fanfare Green Ice (1 kg)	300.00	kg		Done
WHMO/00003	Lettuce Fanfare Green Ice (1 kg)	300.00	kg		Done
		925.00		17757:55	

SRS Fig. 5.0 – Crop Rotation Plan Dashboards

SRS Fig. 6.0 – Employee Clocking In / Clocking Out

SRS Fig. 7.0 – Villegas Organiks Online Shop

E. User Acceptance Testing (UAT) Scripts

System Access and Navigation

IT-Facilitated Crop Rotation Planning System				
Test Executed By:				
Test Executed Date:		November 26, 2021		
Application Version:		CRPS version 1.0		
Test Scope:		System Access and Navigation		
Test Script Document				
TC#	Test Case Item	Test Steps	Expected Result	Test Result
TC00001	Accessing the system	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open the Chrome browser 2. Enter the system URL localhost:8069 3. Press the Enter key 	The user should be able to access the CRPS through the web browser.	☐ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested
TC00002	Accessing the system	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open the Chrome browser 2. Enter the system URL localhost:8069 3. Press the Enter key 	Upon entering the URL, the user should be redirected to the Villegas Organiks website home page.	☐ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested
TC00003	Logging In to the system	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open the Chrome browser 2. Enter the system URL localhost:8069 3. Press the Enter key 4. Click the Sign In hyperlink 5. Enter Email 6. Enter Password 7. Click the Log in button 	The user should be able to log in to the CRPS.	☐ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested
TC00004	Logging In to the system	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open the Chrome browser 2. Enter the system URL localhost:8069 3. Press the Enter key 4. Click the Sign In hyperlink 5. Enter incorrect Email or incorrect Password 6. Click the Log in button 	The user should not be able to log in to the CRPS using an incorrect Email or Password.	☐ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested
TC00005	Logging In to the system	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open the Chrome browser 2. Enter the system URL localhost:8069 	The user should be redirected to the system's Discuss page upon logging in.	☐ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested

IT-Facilitated Crop Rotation Planning System				
Test Executed By:				
Test Executed Date:	November 26, 2021			
Application Version:	CRPS version 1.0			
Test Scope:	System Access and Navigation			
Test Script Document				
TC#	Test Case Item	Test Steps	Expected Result	Test Result
		3. Press the Enter key 4. Click the Sign In hyperlink 5. Enter Email 6. Enter Password 7. Click the Log in button		
TC00006	Logging out of the system	1. Open the Chrome browser 2. Enter the system URL localhost:8069 3. Press the Enter key 4. Click the Sign In hyperlink 5. Enter Email 6. Enter Password 7. Click the Log in button 8. Go to User's Profile 9. Click the Log out button	The system should log out the user from the system upon clicking the Log Out button.	☐ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested
TC00007	System Navigation	1. Open the Chrome browser 2. Enter the system URL localhost:8069 3. Press the Enter key 4. Click the Sign In hyperlink 5. Enter Email 6. Enter Password 7. Click the Log in button 8. Click the Hamburger Menu 9. Check the menu items	The user should be able to see the system menu based on his/her access rights. For End-User: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Discuss ▪ Notes ▪ Contacts ▪ Sales ▪ Invoicing ▪ Website ▪ Events ▪ Purchase ▪ Inventory ▪ Manufacturing ▪ Employees ▪ Attendance ▪ Expenses ▪ Live Chat ▪ Dashboards 	☐ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested

IT-Facilitated Crop Rotation Planning System				
Test Executed By:				
Test Executed Date:	November 26, 2021			
Application Version:	CRPS version 1.0			
Test Scope:	System Access and Navigation			
Test Script Document				
TC#	Test Case Item	Test Steps	Expected Result	Test Result
			For System Admin: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ All End User's Modules ▪ Apps ▪ Settings 	
Comments				

System Administration

IT-Facilitated Crop Rotation Planning System					
Test Executed By:					
Test Executed Date:	November 26, 2021				
Application Version:	CRPS version 1.0				
Test Scope:	System Administration				
Test Script Document					
TC#	Test Case Item	Responsible User	Test Steps (Menu Path)	Expected Result	Test Result
TC00001	System Settings – Organization Structure Definition	System Administrator	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Settings 2. Users & Companies 3. Companies 4. Create button 5. Fill up required fields 6. Click the Save button 	System administrator to set up Villegas Organiks organization information: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Company Name ▪ Address ▪ Company Logo ▪ Phone ▪ Mobile ▪ Email ▪ Website ▪ Tax ID ▪ Currency 	☐ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested
TC00002	System Settings – Document Layout Configuration	System Administrator	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Settings 2. General Settings 3. Companies section 4. Document Layout 	System Administrator to configure the layout of system document: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Layout ▪ Font 	☐ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested

IT-Facilitated Crop Rotation Planning System					
Test Executed By:					
Test Executed Date:		November 26, 2021			
Application Version:		CRPS version 1.0			
Test Scope:		System Administration			
Test Script Document					
TC#	Test Case Item	Responsible User	Test Steps (Menu Path)	Expected Result	Test Result
			sub-section 5. Click Configure Document Layout	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Company Logo ▪ Colors ▪ Layout Background ▪ Company Tagline ▪ Company Details ▪ Footer ▪ Page Format 	
TC00003	System Settings – Document Layout Preview	System Administrator	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Settings 2. General Settings 3. Companies section 4. Document Layout sub-section 5. Click Configure Document Layout 6. Save changes made 7. Click Download PDF Preview 	The system administrator should be able to download a PDF preview of the document layout	☐ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested
TC00004	System Settings – Unit of Measure Definition	System Administrator	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Settings 2. General Settings 3. Units of Measure section 	The system administrator should be able to define the system weight unit of measure (Kilograms) and volume unit of measure (Cubic Meters).	☐ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested

IT-Facilitated Crop Rotation Planning System					
Test Executed By:					
Test Executed Date:	November 26, 2021				
Application Version:	CRPS version 1.0				
Test Scope:	System Administration				
Test Script Document					
TC#	Test Case Item	Responsible User	Test Steps (Menu Path)	Expected Result	Test Result
TC00005	System Settings – User Creation	System Administrator	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Settings Users & Companies Users Click Create button Define User Save changes 	<p>The system administrator should be able to create users in the system.</p> <p>The user should have access to the system after accessing the email invitation link sent by the Administrator.</p>	☐ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested
TC00006	System Settings – Access Rights	System Administrator	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Settings Users & Companies Users Click Create button Define User Set Access Rights Save changes 	<p>The system administrator should be able to define access rights for each system user.</p> <p>The user should only see the system modules defined for his/her account.</p>	☐ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested
TC00007	Report Generation – Users	System Administrator	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Settings Users & Companies Users Click Export button 	<p>The system administrator should be able to generate a report containing the list of users upon clicking the download button in the users' list table.</p> <p>The report should contain the following information:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Name Login Email Address 	☐ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested

IT-Facilitated Crop Rotation Planning System					
Test Executed By:					
Test Executed Date:		November 26, 2021			
Application Version:		CRPS version 1.0			
Test Scope:		System Administration			
Test Script Document					
TC#	Test Case Item	Responsible User	Test Steps (Menu Path)	Expected Result	Test Result
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Language Set ▪ Latest Authentication (Date + Time) 	
Comments					

System Transactions

IT-Facilitated Crop Rotation Planning System					
Test Executed By:					
Test Executed Date:	November 27, 2021				
Application Version:	CRPS version 1.0				
Test Scope:	Inventory Module and Manufacturing Module				
Test Script Document					
TC#	Test Case Item	Responsible User	Test Steps (Menu Path)	Expected Result	Test Result
TC00001	Creation of Product	Operations Manager / Farmer	8. Inventory 9. Products 10. Products	<p>The user should be able to create a new product inventory in the system.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Define Product Name ▪ Define Product Type ▪ Define UoM ▪ Select Product Category ▪ Define Pricing Cost 	☐ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested
				<p>The user should be able to define if the product will be routed for Crop Planning.</p> <p>Operations should be "Manufacture"</p>	☐ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested
TC00002	Updating Qty on Hand	Operations Manager / Farmer	8. Inventory 9. Products 10. Products 11. Select a Product to Update 12. Click Update Quantity	<p>The user should be able to update the quantity on hand of a product.</p> <p>The system should be able to display the updated quantity of the product on the Website.</p>	☐ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested
TC00003	Inventory Report	Operations Manager	4. Inventory 5. Reporting 6. Inventory Report	The Operations Manager should be able to update the Inventory at Date.	☐ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested

IT-Facilitated Crop Rotation Planning System					
Test Executed By:					
Test Executed Date:		November 27, 2021			
Application Version:		CRPS version 1.0			
Test Scope:		Inventory Module and Manufacturing Module			
Test Script Document					
TC#	Test Case Item	Responsible User	Test Steps (Menu Path)	Expected Result	Test Result
				<p>The Operations Manager should be able to download an excel copy of inventory stocks.</p> <p>The Operations Manager should be able to see the forecasted inventory based on the available manufacturing order (crop plan) cycle.</p>	
TC00004	Creation of Fields and Beddings	Operations Manager	7. Manufacturing 8. Configuration 9. Work Centers	The Operations Manager should be able to define all fields and beddings for the farm.	☐ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested
TC00005	Definition of Crop Rotation Operations	Operations Manager	1. Manufacturing 2. Configuration 3. Operations	<p>The Operations Manager should be able to define the crop rotation operations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Land Preparation ▪ Sowing to Emergence ▪ Emergence to Transplanting ▪ Transplanting to Harvest 	☐ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested
TC00006	Crop Rotation Bill of Materials	Operations Manager	1. Manufacturing 2. Products 3. Bill of Materials	The Operations Manager should be able to define the components and operations for each crop item.	☐ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested

IT-Facilitated Crop Rotation Planning System					
Test Executed By:					
Test Executed Date:		November 27, 2021			
Application Version:		CRPS version 1.0			
Test Scope:		Inventory Module and Manufacturing Module			
Test Script Document					
TC#	Test Case Item	Responsible User	Test Steps (Menu Path)	Expected Result	Test Result
TC00007	Crop Planning	Operations Manager	5. Manufacturing 6. Operations 7. Manufacturing Order 8. Click Create button	<p>The Operations Manager should be able to define a new crop to produce.</p> <p>The Operations Manager should be able to select the operation items needed for the Crop Production.</p>	☐ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested
TC00008	Work Orders	Farmers	1. Manufacturing 2. Operations 3. Work Orders 4. Select Work Order 5. Click Start/Block	<p>The Farmer should be able to change the status of each work order for the crop production.</p>	☐ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested
Comments					

F. User Acceptance Testing (UAT) Results

IT-FACILITATED CROP ROTATION PLANNING SYSTEM – USER ACCEPTANCE TESTING SCRIPT DOCUMENT

I hereby confirm that all stated result is correct and valid.

Results:

JOSHUA B. VILLEGAS 11/26/21
 Tester Name | Signature | Date

Passed	
Failed	
Not Tested	
Total Items	

IT-FACILITATED CROP ROTATION PLANNING SYSTEM – USER ACCEPTANCE TESTING SCRIPT DOCUMENT

IT-Facilitated Crop Rotation Planning System

Test Executed By:	JOSHUA B. VILLEGAS
Test Executed Date:	November 26, 2021
Application Version:	CRPS version 1.0
Test Scope:	System Administration

Test Script Document

TC#	Test Case Item	Responsible User	Test Steps (Menu Path)	Expected Result	Test Result
TC00006	System Settings – Access Rights	System Administrator	1. Settings 2. Users & Companies 3. Users 4. Click Create button 5. Define User 6. Set Access Rights 7. Save changes	The system administrator should be able to define access rights for each system user. The user should only see the system modules defined for his/her account.	☒ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested
TC00007	Report Generation – Users	System Administrator	1. Settings 2. Users & Companies 3. Users 4. Click the download (arrow down) button	The system administrator should be able to generate a report containing the list of users upon clicking the download button in the users' list table. The report should contain the following information: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Name Login Email Address Language Set Latest Authentication (Date + Time) 	☒ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested

Comments

IT-Facilitated Crop Rotation Planning System					
Test Executed By:		JOSHUA B. VILLEGAS			
Test Executed Date:		November 26, 2021			
Application Version:		CRPS version 1.0			
Test Scope:		System Administration			
Test Script Document					
TC#	Test Case Item	Responsible User	Test Steps (Menu Path)	Expected Result	Test Result
TC00003	System Settings – Document Layout Preview	System Administrator	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Settings General Settings Companies section Document Layout sub-section Click Configure Document Layout Save changes made Click Download PDF Preview 	The system administrator should be able to download a PDF preview of the document layout	☒ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested
TC00004	System Settings – Unit of Measure Definition	System Administrator	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Settings General Settings Units of Measure section 	The system administrator should be able to define the system weight unit of measure (Kilograms) and volume unit of measure (Cubic Meters).	☒ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested
TC00005	System Settings – User Creation	System Administrator	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Settings Users & Companies Users Click Create button Define User Save changes 	The system administrator should be able to create users in the system. The user should have access to the system after accessing the email invitation link sent by the Administrator.	☒ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested

IT-Facilitated Crop Rotation Planning System					
Test Executed By:		JOSHUA B. VILLEGAS			
Test Executed Date:		November 26, 2021			
Application Version:		CRPS version 1.0			
Test Scope:		System Administration			
Test Script Document					
TC#	Test Case Item	Responsible User	Test Steps (Menu Path)	Expected Result	Test Result
TC00001	System Settings – Organization Structure Definition	System Administrator	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Settings Users & Companies Companies Create button Fill up required fields Click the Save button 	System administrator to set up Villegas Organiks organization information: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Company Name Address Company Logo Phone Mobile Email Website Tax ID Currency 	☒ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested
TC00002	System Settings – Document Layout Configuration	System Administrator	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Settings General Settings Companies section Document Layout sub-section Click Configure Document Layout 	System Administrator to configure the layout of system document: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Layout Font Company Logo Colors Layout Background Company Tagline Company Details Footer Page Format 	☐ Passed ☒ Failed ☐ Not Tested Odo Client Error

I hereby confirm that all stated result is correct and valid.

Results:

JOSHUA B. VILLEGAS 11/26/21
 Tester Name | Signature | Date

Passed	
Failed	
Not Tested	
Total Items	

IT-Facilitated Crop Rotation Planning System

Test Executed By:	JOSHUA B. VILLEGAS
Test Executed Date:	November 26, 2021
Application Version:	CRPS version 1.0
Test Scope:	System Access and Navigation

Test Script Document

TC#	Test Case Item	Test Steps	Expected Result	Test Result
		6. Enter Password 7. Click the Log in button 8. Click the Hamburger Menu 9. Check the menu items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Notes ▪ Contacts ▪ Sales ▪ Invoicing ▪ Website ▪ Events ▪ Purchase ▪ Inventory ▪ Manufacturing ▪ Employees ▪ Attendance ▪ Expenses ▪ Live Chat ▪ Dashboards <p>For System Admin:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ All End User's Modules ▪ Apps ▪ Settings 	

Comments Accessing the system is pretty straightforward. I would recommend having the home page go straight to "Dashboard" instead of "Discuss" page. Trainings for knowledge transfer is needed to fully utilize the system.

IT-Facilitated Crop Rotation Planning System				
Test Executed By:		JOSHUA B. VILLEGAS		
Test Executed Date:		November 26, 2021		
Application Version:		CRPS version 1.0		
Test Scope:		System Access and Navigation		
Test Script Document				
TC#	Test Case Item	Test Steps	Expected Result	Test Result
TC00005	Logging In to the system	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Open the Chrome browser Enter the system URL localhost:8069 Press the Enter key Click the Sign In hyperlink Enter Email Enter Password Click the Log in button 	The user should be redirected to the system's Discuss page upon logging in.	☒ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested
TC00006	Logging out of the system	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Open the Chrome browser Enter the system URL localhost:8069 Press the Enter key Click the Sign In hyperlink Enter Email Enter Password Click the Log in button Go to User's Profile Click the Log out button 	The system should log out the user from the system upon clicking the Log Out button.	☒ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested
TC00007	System Navigation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Open the Chrome browser Enter the system URL localhost:8069 Press the Enter key Click the Sign In hyperlink Enter Email 	The user should be able to see the system menu based on his/her access rights. For End-User: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discuss 	☒ Passed <i>sys. ad</i> ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested

IT-Facilitated Crop Rotation Planning System				
Test Executed By:		JOSHUA B. VILLEGAS		
Test Executed Date:		November 26, 2021		
Application Version:		CRPS version 1.0		
Test Scope:		System Access and Navigation		
Test Script Document				
TC#	Test Case Item	Test Steps	Expected Result	Test Result
TC00001	Accessing the system	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Open the Chrome browser Enter the system URL localhost:8069 Press the Enter key 	The user should be able to access the CRPS through the web browser.	☒ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested
TC00002	Accessing the system	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Open the Chrome browser Enter the system URL localhost:8069 Press the Enter key 	Upon entering the URL, the user should be redirected to the Villegas Organiks website home page.	☒ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested
TC00003	Logging In to the system	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Open the Chrome browser Enter the system URL localhost:8069 Press the Enter key Click the Sign In hyperlink Enter Email Enter Password Click the Log in button 	The user should be able to log in to the CRPS.	☒ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested
TC00004	Logging In to the system	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Open the Chrome browser Enter the system URL localhost:8069 Press the Enter key Click the Sign In hyperlink Enter incorrect Email or incorrect Password 	The user should not be able to log in to the CRPS using an incorrect Email or Password.	☒ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested

I hereby confirm that all stated result is correct and valid.

Results:

MARA CHRISTINE BALADAD

Tester Name | Signature | Date

Passed	7
Failed	0
Not Tested	7
Total Items	7

IT-Facilitated Crop Rotation Planning System				
Test Executed By:		TIN		
Test Executed Date:		November 26, 2021		
Application Version:		CRPS version 1.0		
Test Scope:		System Access and Navigation		
Test Script Document				
TC#	Test Case Item	Test Steps	Expected Result	Test Result
TC00005	Logging In to the system	6. Click the Log in button 1. Open the Chrome browser 2. Enter the system URL localhost:8069 3. Press the Enter key 4. Click the Sign In hyperlink 5. Enter Email 6. Enter Password 7. Click the Log in button	The user should be redirected to the system's Discuss page upon logging in.	☒ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested
TC00006	Logging out of the system	1. Open the Chrome browser 2. Enter the system URL localhost:8069 3. Press the Enter key 4. Click the Sign In hyperlink 5. Enter Email 6. Enter Password 7. Click the Log in button 8. Go to User's Profile 9. Click the Log out button	The system should log out the user from the system upon clicking the Log Out button.	☒ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested
TC00007	System Navigation	1. Open the Chrome browser 2. Enter the system URL localhost:8069 3. Press the Enter key 4. Click the Sign In hyperlink 5. Enter Email	The user should be able to see the system menu based on his/her access rights. For End-User: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Discuss 	☒ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested

IT-Facilitated Crop Rotation Planning System				
Test Executed By:		TIN		
Test Executed Date:		November 26, 2021		
Application Version:		CRPS version 1.0		
Test Scope:		System Access and Navigation		
Test Script Document				
TC#	Test Case Item	Test Steps	Expected Result	Test Result
TC00001	Accessing the system	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open the Chrome browser 2. Enter the system URL localhost:8069 3. Press the Enter key 	The user should be able to access the CRPS through the web browser.	☒ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested
TC00002	Accessing the system	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open the Chrome browser 2. Enter the system URL localhost:8069 3. Press the Enter key 	Upon entering the URL, the user should be redirected to the Villegas Organiks website home page.	☒ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested
TC00003	Logging In to the system	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open the Chrome browser 2. Enter the system URL localhost:8069 3. Press the Enter key 4. Click the Sign In hyperlink 5. Enter Email 6. Enter Password 7. Click the Log in button 	The user should be able to log in to the CRPS.	☒ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested
TC00004	Logging In to the system	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open the Chrome browser 2. Enter the system URL localhost:8069 3. Press the Enter key 4. Click the Sign In hyperlink 5. Enter incorrect Email or incorrect Password 	The user should not be able to log in to the CRPS using an incorrect Email or Password.	☒ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested

IT-Facilitated Crop Rotation Planning System				
Test Executed By:		BEN		
Test Executed Date:		November 26, 2021		
Application Version:		CRPS version 1.0		
Test Scope:		System Access and Navigation		
Test Script Document				
TC#	Test Case Item	Test Steps	Expected Result	Test Result
		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. Enter Password 7. Click the Log in button 8. Click the Hamburger Menu 9. Check the menu items 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Notes ▪ Contacts ▪ Sales ▪ Invoicing ▪ Website ▪ Events ▪ Purchase ▪ Inventory ▪ Manufacturing ▪ Employees ▪ Attendance ▪ Expenses ▪ Live Chat ▪ Dashboards <p>For System Admin:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ All End User's Modules ▪ Apps ▪ Settings 	PASSED
Comments				

I hereby confirm that all stated result is correct and valid.

Results:

BERNI

Tester Name | Signature | Date

Passed	7
Failed	0
Not Tested	0
Total Items	7

IT-FACILITATED CROP ROTATION PLANNING SYSTEM – USER ACCEPTANCE TESTING SCRIPT DOCUMENT

IT-Facilitated Crop Rotation Planning System

Test Executed By:	BERNI
Test Executed Date:	November 26, 2021
Application Version:	CRPS version 1.0
Test Scope:	System Access and Navigation

Test Script Document

TC#	Test Case Item	Test Steps	Expected Result	Test Result
TC00001	Accessing the system	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open the Chrome browser 2. Enter the system URL localhost:8069 3. Press the Enter key 	The user should be able to access the CRPS through the web browser.	☒ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested
TC00002	Accessing the system	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open the Chrome browser 2. Enter the system URL localhost:8069 3. Press the Enter key 	Upon entering the URL, the user should be redirected to the Villegas Organiks website home page.	☒ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested
TC00003	Logging In to the system	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open the Chrome browser 2. Enter the system URL localhost:8069 3. Press the Enter key 4. Click the Sign In hyperlink 5. Enter Email 6. Enter Password 7. Click the Log in button 	The user should be able to log in to the CRPS.	☒ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested
TC00004	Logging In to the system	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open the Chrome browser 2. Enter the system URL localhost:8069 3. Press the Enter key 4. Click the Sign In hyperlink 5. Enter incorrect Email or incorrect Password 	The user should not be able to log in to the CRPS using an incorrect Email or Password.	☒ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested

IT-FACILITATED CROP ROTATION PLANNING SYSTEM – USER ACCEPTANCE TESTING SCRIPT DOCUMENT

IT-Facilitated Crop Rotation Planning System				
Test Executed By:	BERN			
Test Executed Date:	November 26, 2021			
Application Version:	CRPS version 1.0			
Test Scope:	System Access and Navigation			
Test Script Document				
TC#	Test Case Item	Test Steps	Expected Result	Test Result
TC00005	Logging In to the system	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. Click the Log in button 1. Open the Chrome browser 2. Enter the system URL localhost:8069 3. Press the Enter key 4. Click the Sign In hyperlink 5. Enter Email 6. Enter Password 7. Click the Log in button 	The user should be redirected to the system's Discuss page upon logging in.	☒ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested
TC00006	Logging out of the system	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open the Chrome browser 2. Enter the system URL localhost:8069 3. Press the Enter key 4. Click the Sign In hyperlink 5. Enter Email 6. Enter Password 7. Click the Log in button 8. Go to User's Profile 9. Click the Log out button 	The system should log out the user from the system upon clicking the Log Out button.	☒ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested
TC00007	System Navigation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open the Chrome browser 2. Enter the system URL localhost:8069 3. Press the Enter key 4. Click the Sign In hyperlink 5. Enter Email 	The user should be able to see the system menu based on his/her access rights. For End-User: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discuss 	☒ Passed ☐ Failed ☐ Not Tested

G. Odoo Helpful Links

Inventory: Odoo Inventory is both an inventory application and a warehouse management system

[Odoo Tutorials: Inventory](#)
[Odoo Documentation: Inventory](#)

Manufacturing. Odoo Manufacturing is an app used to schedule, plan and process manufacturing orders, work orders, control the work center, trigger maintenance operations, feedback loops, quality issues, etc.

[Odoo Tutorials: MRP](#)
[Odoo Documentation: Manufacturing Management](#)

** NOTHING FOLLOWS**